
TaphArt: exploring the potential existence of rock art paintings in the Middle Stone Age of southern Africa and its destruction due to the action of taphonomic processes, DMP of project

Plan de gestion de données créé à l'aide de DMP OPIDoR, basé sur le modèle "Horizon Europe DMP (english)" fourni par Commission européenne.

Plan Details

Plan title	TaphArt: exploring the potential existence of rock art paintings in the Middle Stone Age of southern Africa and its destruction due to the action of taphonomic processes, DMP of project
Deliverable	Deliverable D1.2
Version	Final version
Plan purpose/scope	<p>This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the strategy for managing research data generated throughout the TaphArt project (Grant Agreement No. 101109977). The purpose of this plan is to ensure that all data produced are managed in accordance with the FAIR principles—Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable—and in compliance with Horizon Europe and institutional requirements regarding data stewardship, open science, and long-term preservation. The scope of the plan includes all datasets generated during fieldwork, laboratory experiments, and dissemination activities related to the investigation of taphonomic processes affecting potential Middle Stone Age rock art in southern Africa. This includes photographic and video documentation, analytical imagery (3D microscope, EDXRF, hyperspectral), experimental data, and dissemination outputs. The DMP is closely aligned with other project deliverables, particularly:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific deliverables, such as journal articles and datasets, which are supported by the data management strategy to ensure proper documentation, traceability, and reproducibility. • Open Access publications, for which the underlying data will be made openly available in trusted repositories (Zenodo) at the time of submission. • Dissemination reports, which rely on media and documentation that are also covered by the DMP in terms of preservation and reuse. • Career Development and Research Output plans, which benefit from the transparent and structured handling of research data as part of good scientific practice. <p>This plan will be updated as needed during the project to reflect any changes in data workflows or repository arrangements, and to document the final status of each dataset at project completion.</p>

Fields of science and technology (from OECD classification)	History and archaeology, Materials engineering, Earth and related environmental sciences, Arts (arts, history of arts, performing arts, music)
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Language	eng
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Creation date	2025-05-23
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Last modification date	2025-08-19
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Identifier type	DOI
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License	<table border="0"> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top;">Name</td> <td>Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="vertical-align: top;">URL</td> <td>http://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.json</td> </tr> </table>	Name	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	URL	http://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-4.0.json
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Project Details

Project title	TaphArt: exploring the potential existence of rock art paintings in the Middle Stone Age of southern Africa and its destruction due to the action of taphonomic processes
Acronym	TaphArt
Abstract	"The advent of symbolic material culture and the storage of information outside the human brain through the production of artefacts and images imbued with meaning was a landmark in human evolution. Although it has been generally considered as the consequence of an European Upper Palaeolithic ""revolution"" that took place around 40 ka, new evidence from the Middle Stone Age (MSA, ~30040 ka) suggests the presence of symbolic material culture in Africa at ~150 ka. In this context, a major research challenge for archaeology is to explain the apparent absence of rock art paintings in the MSA archaeological record of southern Africa. Ochre pigments are ubiquitous in the sites from this period, and toolkits used to produce ochre-rich liquid paint date from at least ~100 ka. Furthermore, images engraved on pieces of ochre and a crayon drawing demonstrate that the MSA populations had all the material, technical and cognitive resources necessary to create graphic representations. Thus, through an innovative and interdisciplinary approach that brings together archaeology, paleoenvironmental science, atmospheric science, material science, and analytical chemistry, the TaphArt project aims to develop an experimental research to determine whether the absence of rock art paintings in the MSA sites of southern Africa is due to a cultural choice of the human populations or the result of taphonomic processes that eliminated the painted images from the archaeological record. Taking as reference the archaeological and paleoenvironmental context of Blombos Cave (South Africa), the project tests the hypothesis that marine aerosol and wind erosion may have contributed to the destruction of rock art paintings potentially produced on the site, providing groundbreaking unprecedented data to the discussion on the origins of rock art and the behavioural evolution of the Homo sapiens."
Funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission : https://doi.org/10.3030/101109977 • European Commission : https://doi.org/10.3030/101109977
Start date	2023-09-01
End date	2025-08-31
Partners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UNIVERSITE DE BORDEAUX • UNIVERSIDAD DEL PAIS VASCO/ EUSKAL HERRIKO UNIBERTSITATEA • UNIVERSITE DE BORDEAUX • UNIVERSIDAD DEL PAIS VASCO/ EUSKAL HERRIKO UNIBERTSITATEA
Research outputs :	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Photographs and videos of the fieldworks carried out in the Blombos cave area (South Africa) (Dataset) 2. Photographs of each stage of the experiments on the impact of wind erosion and marine aerosol degradation on rock art paintings (Dataset)

3. Photographs of experimental rock art paintings before, during, and after degradation experiments (Dataset)
4. 3D microscope images of experimental rock art paintings taken during degradation experiments (Dataset)
5. Micro EDXRF mapping images of experimental rock art paintings taken during degradation experiments (Dataset)
6. Hyperspectral images of experimental rock art paintings taken during degradation experiments (Dataset)
7. Numerical data from analysis using 3D microscopy, micro EDXRF mapping and hyperspectral imaging (Dataset)
8. Datasets compiling numerical data generated during the experiments (Dataset)
9. Project documents (career development plan, DMP, dissemination plan, journal articles, datasets) (Text)
10. Photographs and videos of dissemination activities carried out during the project (Audiovisual)

Contributors

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UNIVERSITE DE BORDEAUX	UNIVERSITE DE BORDEAUX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project coordinator

TaphArt: exploring the potential existence of rock art paintings in the Middle Stone Age of southern Africa and its destruction due to the action of taphonomic processes, DMP of project

Photographs and videos of the fieldworks carried out in the Blombos cave area (South Africa)

1. Data Summary

- **Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.**
- **What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?**
- **What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?**
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- **To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?**

The dataset "FW\ PHOTO\ VIDEO" consists of original photographs and videos taken during fieldwork at the Blombos Cave area in South Africa. No existing data will be reused, as the project is based on novel investigations in a specific archaeological and environmental context. The data will be generated in high-resolution formats, including RAW and JPG for images and MP4 for videos, and is expected to reach approximately 150 GB in total size.

The primary purpose of this dataset is to visually document the environmental and archaeological setting of the site under study. It supports the overall objectives of the TaphArt project by providing empirical material that captures the field conditions relevant to the investigation of taphonomic processes, particularly wind erosion and marine aerosol impacts on potential rock art. These visual records are critical for contextualizing the experimental work conducted in the laboratory and validating the parameters used in degradation simulations.

The data will be generated by the research team during on-site campaigns conducted under the coordination of the Université de Bordeaux, in collaboration with local partners and authorities. Beyond the immediate needs of the project, the dataset will be of interest to archaeologists working in Middle Stone Age contexts, heritage professionals focusing on rock art conservation, environmental scientists studying site exposure and erosion, and educators looking for high-quality visual content related to field-based archaeological research.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- **Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?**
- **Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.**
- **Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?**
- **Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?**

All datasets generated by the TaphArt project will be assigned a persistent identifier (DOI) upon deposit, ensuring stable and long-term accessibility. The primary repository foreseen is Zenodo, which automatically assigns DOIs and complies with OpenAIRE guidelines. In parallel, the project is exploring the use of Nakala, the French trusted repository operated by TGIR Huma-Num, which also supports DOI assignment through DataCite and offers long-term preservation on national infrastructure.

For datasets with high disciplinary value in archaeology (e.g. experimental imaging, geochemical analyses, context-specific datasets), the project will evaluate the possibility of depositing through a national node of ARIADNEplus, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS, UK) or DANS (Netherlands), depending on suitability and institutional agreements.

Rich metadata will be created for all datasets, including descriptive elements such as title, authorship, institutional affiliation, abstract, keywords, date and location of data collection, methodology, file formats, licensing, and funding references. Metadata

will comply with the DataCite schema (Zenodo and Nakala) and, where applicable, will be aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM) for archaeological content. This ensures semantic interoperability and integration into disciplinary and general discovery platforms.

Keywords will be systematically provided to support discovery and reuse, with particular attention to terms relevant to Middle Stone Age archaeology, experimental rock art degradation, imaging techniques, and conservation science.

All metadata will be published openly and structured in machine-readable formats, ensuring compatibility with standard harvesting protocols such as OAI-PMH. This will enable indexing by OpenAIRE, EOSC, and other aggregators, guaranteeing that datasets are discoverable by both human users and automated services.

2.2.1. Making data accessible : Repository

- **Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?**
- **Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?**
- **Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?**

TaphArt datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories that meet the requirements for FAIR data, long-term accessibility, and OpenAIRE compliance. The primary repository chosen is Zenodo, maintained by CERN and supported by the European Commission. Zenodo is widely used by Horizon Europe projects, ensures robust infrastructure, immediate open access, and automatic DOI assignment.

In addition, the project will consider depositing in Nakala, the national repository for humanities and social sciences operated by TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS). Nakala is a certified repository based in France, providing stable hosting, persistent identifiers (via DataCite), and disciplinary support for research outputs in archaeology and cultural heritage.

For datasets of high archaeological relevance, especially those intended for international reuse or integration in heritage infrastructures, the project will evaluate deposition through the ARIADNEplus infrastructure via an appropriate national node, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) or DANS. This option will be prioritized for datasets that benefit from enriched archaeological metadata and curation.

Exploratory steps have been taken to review the submission procedures, metadata requirements, and licensing conditions for Zenodo and Nakala. The project team is also initiating contacts with ARIADNEplus nodes to assess the feasibility of deposition. All repositories under consideration ensure that datasets are assigned a DOI, which is a persistent and resolvable identifier linking directly to the dataset landing page, enabling durable access and citation.

2.2.2. Making data accessible : Data

- **Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.**
- **If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.**
- **Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?**
- **If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?**
- **How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?**
- **Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?**

All data generated by the TaphArt project will be made openly available as a matter of principle, in alignment with Horizon Europe's open science policies and the project's commitment to transparency, reproducibility, and societal impact. No legal, contractual, ethical, or privacy-related constraints apply to the datasets produced, as the project does not involve personal data or commercially sensitive information. All datasets are based on non-invasive experiments, scientific imaging, and dissemination activities involving consenting participants or publicly accessible materials.

An embargo period may be applied in selected cases to allow for the preparation and submission of peer-reviewed publications. In such cases, data will be made openly available at the time of submission of the related publication, in accordance with the project's data sharing policy. Embargo periods, if any, will not exceed six months from the time of data generation, and each dataset record will clearly indicate its availability date.

All data will be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol, such as HTTPS, ensuring open and unrestricted access via the landing page of the repository (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus node). Each dataset will include a persistent and resolvable DOI that points directly to a public record and download options, without the need for user registration or authentication.

Since all data are intended to be open access and no personal or sensitive data are processed, no restrictions on access are

foreseen during or after the project. If exceptional access limitations arise (e.g. embargo, third-party copyright), the repository's access control features will be used to temporarily restrict access while providing appropriate metadata and contact information for users seeking early access.

The identity of users accessing the data will not be tracked, as the datasets will be fully open and do not require login or authentication. Download metrics may be collected by the repositories for statistical purposes only.

There is no need for a data access committee, as none of the datasets involve sensitive, personal, or ethically regulated content requiring evaluation of access requests.

2.2.3. Making data accessible : Metadata

- **Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?**
- **How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?**
- **Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**

All metadata associated with the datasets produced by the TaphArt project will be made openly available and published under the CC0 public domain dedication, in compliance with the requirements of the Grant Agreement. This will allow for automatic indexing by platforms such as OpenAIRE and integration into disciplinary catalogues. Each metadata record will include a persistent identifier (DOI) and complete information enabling direct access to the corresponding dataset.

The metadata will include all necessary elements to facilitate access to and reuse of the datasets: title, authors, date, file formats, licensing terms, access protocol, storage location, embargo period (if applicable), and direct links to downloadable files.

All metadata records will explicitly indicate that the dataset was produced under the Horizon Europe TaphArt project (Grant Agreement No. 101109977), ensuring compliance with funder requirements and enabling automatic linkage via OpenAIRE.

The data will be preserved for a minimum of ten years, in accordance with European best practices and the retention policies of the selected repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or an ARIADNEplus node). Even in the event that a dataset must be withdrawn, the corresponding metadata record will remain available as a tombstone page, maintaining citation integrity and reference continuity.

The project does not develop software as a standalone research product, but scripts and data processing code will be produced as part of the data analysis workflow. These scripts (e.g. for image processing, data normalization, or statistical comparison) will be shared alongside the relevant datasets under open-source licenses such as MIT or GPL, and will be deposited in Zenodo, with persistent links included in the associated metadata records.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- **What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?**
- **In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?**
- **Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?**

The TaphArt project will ensure data interoperability by using well-established data formats, disciplinary metadata standards, and community-endorsed best practices. All datasets will be formatted in widely used and open formats such as CSV, XLSX, TIFF, JPG, RAW, MP4, ENVI, and HDF5, ensuring compatibility across platforms and disciplines.

Metadata will be structured using the DataCite schema (for Zenodo and Nakala) and, where appropriate, aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM), which is the community-endorsed standard for archaeological datasets. The ACDM provides semantic consistency and facilitates integration into broader infrastructures such as ARIADNEplus, OpenAIRE, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). For tabular and numerical data, standard variable naming and unit conventions will be followed to maximize readability and compatibility.

In case the project generates project-specific vocabularies or uses non-standard terminologies (for instance, for experimental categories or environmental simulation parameters), a mapping to common ontologies will be provided when possible. These vocabularies or classifications will be openly published to enable reuse, refinement, and extension by other researchers.

Where relevant, datasets will include qualified references to other datasets produced within the project (e.g. linking image files to corresponding numerical analysis outputs) or to external datasets used as comparative baselines. These links will be established using persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs or URIs) and clearly described in the metadata to enable structured cross-referencing and semantic interoperability.

The project team is committed to following interoperability best practices promoted by the FAIR principles, including the use of machine-readable formats, standardized variable names, and clear licensing and provenance declarations.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- **How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?**
- **Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?**
- **Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?**
- **Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?**
- **Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.**
- **Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.**

To ensure maximum data re-use, the TaphArt project will provide comprehensive documentation alongside each dataset. This will include structured README files detailing the methodology, data collection context, file structure, variable definitions, units of measurement, software requirements (if applicable), and any data cleaning or transformation procedures applied. For numerical datasets, codebooks and examples of analytical workflows will be included. For imaging and video datasets, metadata will indicate acquisition parameters, equipment used, and pre/post-processing steps. All documentation will be in English and structured to support understanding and reuse by both domain experts and interdisciplinary users.

All datasets will be made freely available in the public domain under standard open licenses that permit broad reuse. The default license will be CC BY 4.0, unless there is a specific need to apply CC0 (for metadata or non-attributable content) or another recognized license. This licensing approach complies with the obligations set out in the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and ensures legal clarity for data reuse.

The datasets will be structured and documented in such a way that they remain usable by third parties, including after the project ends. Persistent identifiers (DOIs) will be assigned to all datasets, and hosting in trusted repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus) will guarantee their long-term availability and accessibility, typically for at least 10 years.

Provenance will be fully documented using accepted metadata standards (e.g. DataCite, ACDM), indicating the origin of the data, institutions and researchers involved, instruments or software used, and processing history. When datasets derive from previous project outputs (e.g. linking raw image data to post-processed files or analysis tables), qualified references will be included to establish transparent data lineage.

The project will apply several data quality assurance measures: calibration of instruments and imaging systems prior to data acquisition, use of validated protocols for experiments and environmental simulation, consistency checks between datasets and documentation, peer-review of code/scripts used in data analysis, version control of files and clear labelling of file types and revisions.

In line with the broader FAIR principles, the project also addresses outputs beyond datasets. Scientific publications will be deposited in open access, and code or scripts developed for data analysis will be shared under open-source licenses. Data security during the project is ensured through regular backups and institutional storage infrastructure. No personal or sensitive data are processed, and no ethical approvals are required, as all data originate from non-invasive experimental setups and public dissemination activities.

The project allocates the necessary resources—both technical and human—to support good data management throughout its lifecycle, with dedicated support from the hosting institution (Université de Bordeaux) and external infrastructure partners.

3. Other research outputs

- **In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).**
- **Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.**

In addition to research data, the TaphArt project will generate a number of other research outputs, primarily in digital form. These include data analysis scripts, image processing workflows, experimental protocols, and documentation for laboratory simulations related to environmental degradation processes. While the project does not produce software or physical outputs (such as biological samples or new materials), the digital research objects created will be managed according to the same FAIR principles as datasets.

All scripts and workflows developed for processing 3D images, hyperspectral data, or numerical analysis (e.g. statistical

comparisons, time-series modeling) will be documented, versioned, and made openly available in open-source repositories such as Zenodo. These will include clear descriptions of dependencies, usage instructions, licensing terms (e.g. MIT or GPL), and links to example datasets when appropriate. Protocols for the experimental simulation of taphonomic processes will be provided as standalone documents (e.g. PDF or Markdown) and will be deposited alongside the datasets they support.

Metadata for these research outputs will include references to related datasets, the project's funding information (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101109977), and licensing conditions, ensuring they are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs) will be assigned to ensure long-term accessibility and citability. Where appropriate, qualified references to external standards or existing methods (e.g. those published in scientific literature or in public repositories like protocols.io) will also be included.

By managing these outputs transparently and openly, the project ensures that not only the data, but the entire analytical and experimental workflow, is reproducible and reusable by the research community—both during and beyond the project lifetime.

4. Allocation of resources

- **What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?**
- **How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)**
- **Who will be responsible for data management in your project?**
- **How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?**

Costs related to making data and other research outputs FAIR in the TaphArt project are limited but accounted for. They primarily include indirect costs associated with the time needed to document, prepare, and curate datasets, scripts, and protocols for open access deposition; as well as minor direct costs related to long-term storage and archiving in trusted repositories. No external data management service providers are involved.

These efforts are covered by personnel costs already budgeted in the project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) framework. This includes time allocated by the fellow for preparing data and metadata, documenting experimental workflows, and depositing outputs in repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala. The hosting institution, Université de Bordeaux, also provides in-kind support via its Research Data service and access to Huma-Num infrastructure for deposit in Nakala. These resources fall under eligible costs according to the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement.

The person responsible for data management is the MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow (Neemias Santos da Rosa), with support from the Université de Bordeaux Research Data Officer and technical assistance from the institutional IT and research support services.

Long-term preservation will be ensured through the selection of trusted, EOSC-compatible repositories that commit to multi-year storage and persistent access, such as Zenodo, Nakala, or a suitable ARIADNEplus node. These platforms ensure at least 10 years of data availability, with metadata guaranteed to remain available even if the datasets are withdrawn or archived.

The datasets to be preserved long-term include:

- All experimental datasets (raw and processed)
- Associated metadata and documentation
- Analysis scripts and protocols

The decision on what to retain is made by the fellow in coordination with the supervisor and based on the scientific value, potential for reuse, and compliance with Horizon Europe's open science guidelines. No significant financial investment is foreseen for long-term preservation, as the repositories selected offer free or publicly funded services for open-access projects. However, additional backup copies will be maintained on the institution's internal research data servers to provide redundancy and safeguard research integrity.

5. Data security

- **What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?**
- **Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?**

All research data generated during the TaphArt project will be managed using secure and reliable infrastructure provided by the Université de Bordeaux, which ensures compliance with institutional and European standards for data security. During the active

phase of the project, data will be stored on institutional servers with regular automated backups, version control, and access-restricted folders when appropriate. In addition, data are also stored locally on encrypted, access-controlled devices used by the researcher, with periodic manual backups to secure drives.

Although the project does not involve sensitive or personal data, all files are handled with care to prevent loss, corruption, or unauthorized modification. No transfer of confidential or ethically regulated content is expected.

Once validated and prepared for publication, datasets will be transferred to trusted repositories for long-term preservation. These include Zenodo, Nakala (operated by Huma-Num), and possibly a disciplinary repository within ARIADNEplus, all of which guarantee secure storage, open access compliance, and persistent identifiers. These platforms ensure redundant storage, data integrity, and metadata preservation, meeting the requirements for Horizon Europe-funded projects.

The selected repositories are aligned with FAIR principles and provide the technical infrastructure necessary for long-term curation and data recovery. As a result, data security is ensured both during the project and after its completion, supporting sustainable and open research practices.

6. Ethics

- **Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).**
- **Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?**

There are no ethics or legal issues that impact data sharing in the TaphArt project. The research does not involve the collection or processing of personal data, nor does it include any data subject to ethical review (such as human participants, sensitive materials, or restricted cultural heritage content). All experimental procedures involve non-invasive analysis of materials created by the research team, and all dissemination materials (e.g. photographs or videos of outreach events) involve only project members or public audiences in open settings, with no collection of identifiable information.

As such, no informed consent for data sharing or preservation is required, and no personal or sensitive data are included in any dataset generated. This has been clearly stated in the ethics self-assessment submitted during the proposal phase, and confirmed in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethics deliverables are expected for this project, and the data management strategy fully complies with the legal and ethical framework of Horizon Europe, as well as the institutional policies of the Université de Bordeaux.

Should any unforeseen ethical or legal concerns arise (e.g. third-party copyright in dissemination materials), they will be addressed by applying appropriate licensing restrictions or access limitations, and by documenting these conditions transparently in the dataset metadata.

7. Other issues

- **Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?**

In addition to complying with Horizon Europe requirements and the FAIR principles, the TaphArt project also follows national and institutional procedures for data management:

- **Université de Bordeaux Research Data Policy:** The project aligns with the institutional guidelines on responsible research data management, as outlined by the Université de Bordeaux. This includes the use of secure storage infrastructure, good documentation practices, and the recommendation to deposit data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala (Huma-Num).
- **Huma-Num (TGIR) infrastructure:** As a project based in France and hosted by a public research institution, TaphArt has access to the national humanities data infrastructure Huma-Num, which provides long-term preservation services via Nakala, along with guidance on metadata and licensing. Use of Huma-Num services ensures alignment with French national recommendations on open science and digital humanities.
- **Open Science recommendations by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research:** The project contributes to the broader implementation of the French National Plan for Open Science, which promotes free access to research data, interoperability, and reusability, particularly for publicly funded research.

These procedures complement the Horizon Europe open science framework and help ensure the sustainability, legality, and

reusability of the research outputs during and after the project.

Photographs of each stage of the experiments on the impact of wind erosion and marine aerosol degradation on rock art paintings

1. Data Summary

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- **To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?**

The dataset "EXP_STAGE\ IMG" includes photographs documenting each stage of the experimental procedures designed to simulate the impact of wind erosion and marine aerosol degradation on rock art paintings. All data are newly generated within the framework of the TaphArt project; no existing datasets are reused, as the experiments and their documentation are original to this research.

The dataset consists of high-resolution photographic files in RAW and JPG formats. It is expected to reach an approximate size of 100 GB. The purpose of this dataset is to provide detailed visual documentation of the experimental protocol, from the preparation of the painted surfaces to their exposure to controlled taphonomic agents. These images are crucial for monitoring changes over time and serve as a basis for qualitative and quantitative assessments of degradation effects.

The data will be generated by the research team in laboratory settings at the Université de Bordeaux, the University of the Basque Country, and the German Aerospace Center. The photographs will illustrate methodological reproducibility and experimental conditions, supporting transparency and the replicability of findings. This dataset will be of particular interest to researchers working on experimental archaeology, conservation science, and taphonomic modeling, as well as educators seeking materials that illustrate scientific approaches to cultural heritage research.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- **Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?**
- **Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.**
- **Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?**
- **Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?**

All datasets generated by the TaphArt project will be assigned a persistent identifier (DOI) upon deposit, ensuring stable and long-term accessibility. The primary repository foreseen is Zenodo, which automatically assigns DOIs and complies with OpenAIRE guidelines. In parallel, the project is exploring the use of Nakala, the French trusted repository operated by TGIR Huma-Num, which also supports DOI assignment through DataCite and offers long-term preservation on national infrastructure.

For datasets with high disciplinary value in archaeology (e.g. experimental imaging, geochemical analyses, context-specific datasets), the project will evaluate the possibility of depositing through a national node of ARIADNEplus, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS, UK) or DANS (Netherlands), depending on suitability and institutional agreements.

Rich metadata will be created for all datasets, including descriptive elements such as title, authorship, institutional affiliation, abstract, keywords, date and location of data collection, methodology, file formats, licensing, and funding references. Metadata will comply with the DataCite schema (Zenodo and Nakala) and, where applicable, will be aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM) for archaeological content. This ensures semantic interoperability and integration into disciplinary and general discovery platforms.

Keywords will be systematically provided to support discovery and reuse, with particular attention to terms relevant to Middle

Stone Age archaeology, experimental rock art degradation, imaging techniques, and conservation science.

All metadata will be published openly and structured in machine-readable formats, ensuring compatibility with standard harvesting protocols such as OAI-PMH. This will enable indexing by OpenAIRE, EOSC, and other aggregators, guaranteeing that datasets are discoverable by both human users and automated services.

2.2.1. Making data accessible : Repository

- **Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?**
- **Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?**
- **Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?**

TaphArt datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories that meet the requirements for FAIR data, long-term accessibility, and OpenAIRE compliance. The primary repository chosen is Zenodo, maintained by CERN and supported by the European Commission. Zenodo is widely used by Horizon Europe projects, ensures robust infrastructure, immediate open access, and automatic DOI assignment.

In addition, the project will consider depositing in Nakala, the national repository for humanities and social sciences operated by TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS). Nakala is a certified repository based in France, providing stable hosting, persistent identifiers (via DataCite), and disciplinary support for research outputs in archaeology and cultural heritage.

For datasets of high archaeological relevance, especially those intended for international reuse or integration in heritage infrastructures, the project will evaluate deposition through the ARIADNEplus infrastructure via an appropriate national node, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) or DANS. This option will be prioritized for datasets that benefit from enriched archaeological metadata and curation.

Exploratory steps have been taken to review the submission procedures, metadata requirements, and licensing conditions for Zenodo and Nakala. The project team is also initiating contacts with ARIADNEplus nodes to assess the feasibility of deposition. All repositories under consideration ensure that datasets are assigned a DOI, which is a persistent and resolvable identifier linking directly to the dataset landing page, enabling durable access and citation.

2.2.2. Making data accessible : Data

- **Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.**
- **If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.**
- **Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?**
- **If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?**
- **How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?**
- **Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?**

All data generated by the TaphArt project will be made openly available as a matter of principle, in alignment with Horizon Europe's open science policies and the project's commitment to transparency, reproducibility, and societal impact. No legal, contractual, ethical, or privacy-related constraints apply to the datasets produced, as the project does not involve personal data or commercially sensitive information. All datasets are based on non-invasive experiments, scientific imaging, and dissemination activities involving consenting participants or publicly accessible materials.

An embargo period may be applied in selected cases to allow for the preparation and submission of peer-reviewed publications. In such cases, data will be made openly available at the time of submission of the related publication, in accordance with the project's data sharing policy. Embargo periods, if any, will not exceed six months from the time of data generation, and each dataset record will clearly indicate its availability date.

All data will be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol, such as HTTPS, ensuring open and unrestricted access via the landing page of the repository (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus node). Each dataset will include a persistent and resolvable DOI that points directly to a public record and download options, without the need for user registration or authentication.

Since all data are intended to be open access and no personal or sensitive data are processed, no restrictions on access are foreseen during or after the project. If exceptional access limitations arise (e.g. embargo, third-party copyright), the repository's access control features will be used to temporarily restrict access while providing appropriate metadata and contact information for users seeking early access.

The identity of users accessing the data will not be tracked, as the datasets will be fully open and do not require login or

authentication. Download metrics may be collected by the repositories for statistical purposes only.

There is no need for a data access committee, as none of the datasets involve sensitive, personal, or ethically regulated content requiring evaluation of access requests.

2.2.3. Making data accessible : Metadata

- **Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?**
- **How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?**
- **Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**

All metadata associated with the datasets produced by the TaphArt project will be made openly available and published under the CC0 public domain dedication, in compliance with the requirements of the Grant Agreement. This will allow for automatic indexing by platforms such as OpenAIRE and integration into disciplinary catalogues. Each metadata record will include a persistent identifier (DOI) and complete information enabling direct access to the corresponding dataset.

The metadata will include all necessary elements to facilitate access to and reuse of the datasets: title, authors, date, file formats, licensing terms, access protocol, storage location, embargo period (if applicable), and direct links to downloadable files.

All metadata records will explicitly indicate that the dataset was produced under the Horizon Europe TaphArt project (Grant Agreement No. 101109977), ensuring compliance with funder requirements and enabling automatic linkage via OpenAIRE.

The data will be preserved for a minimum of ten years, in accordance with European best practices and the retention policies of the selected repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or an ARIADNEplus node). Even in the event that a dataset must be withdrawn, the corresponding metadata record will remain available as a tombstone page, maintaining citation integrity and reference continuity.

The project does not develop software as a standalone research product, but scripts and data processing code will be produced as part of the data analysis workflow. These scripts (e.g. for image processing, data normalization, or statistical comparison) will be shared alongside the relevant datasets under open-source licenses such as MIT or GPL, and will be deposited in Zenodo, with persistent links included in the associated metadata records.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- **What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?**
- **In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?**
- **Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?**

The TaphArt project will ensure data interoperability by using well-established data formats, disciplinary metadata standards, and community-endorsed best practices. All datasets will be formatted in widely used and open formats such as CSV, XLSX, TIFF, JPG, RAW, MP4, ENVI, and HDF5, ensuring compatibility across platforms and disciplines.

Metadata will be structured using the DataCite schema (for Zenodo and Nakala) and, where appropriate, aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM), which is the community-endorsed standard for archaeological datasets. The ACDM provides semantic consistency and facilitates integration into broader infrastructures such as ARIADNEplus, OpenAIRE, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). For tabular and numerical data, standard variable naming and unit conventions will be followed to maximize readability and compatibility.

In case the project generates project-specific vocabularies or uses non-standard terminologies (for instance, for experimental categories or environmental simulation parameters), a mapping to common ontologies will be provided when possible. These vocabularies or classifications will be openly published to enable reuse, refinement, and extension by other researchers.

Where relevant, datasets will include qualified references to other datasets produced within the project (e.g. linking image files to corresponding numerical analysis outputs) or to external datasets used as comparative baselines. These links will be established using persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs or URIs) and clearly described in the metadata to enable structured cross-referencing and semantic interoperability.

The project team is committed to following interoperability best practices promoted by the FAIR principles, including the use of machine-readable formats, standardized variable names, and clear licensing and provenance declarations.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- **How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?**
- **Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?**
- **Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?**
- **Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?**
- **Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.**
- **Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.**

To ensure maximum data re-use, the TaphArt project will provide comprehensive documentation alongside each dataset. This will include structured README files detailing the methodology, data collection context, file structure, variable definitions, units of measurement, software requirements (if applicable), and any data cleaning or transformation procedures applied. For numerical datasets, codebooks and examples of analytical workflows will be included. For imaging and video datasets, metadata will indicate acquisition parameters, equipment used, and pre/post-processing steps. All documentation will be in English and structured to support understanding and reuse by both domain experts and interdisciplinary users.

All datasets will be made freely available in the public domain under standard open licenses that permit broad reuse. The default license will be CC BY 4.0, unless there is a specific need to apply CC0 (for metadata or non-attributable content) or another recognized license. This licensing approach complies with the obligations set out in the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and ensures legal clarity for data reuse.

The datasets will be structured and documented in such a way that they remain usable by third parties, including after the project ends. Persistent identifiers (DOIs) will be assigned to all datasets, and hosting in trusted repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus) will guarantee their long-term availability and accessibility, typically for at least 10 years.

Provenance will be fully documented using accepted metadata standards (e.g. DataCite, ACDM), indicating the origin of the data, institutions and researchers involved, instruments or software used, and processing history. When datasets derive from previous project outputs (e.g. linking raw image data to post-processed files or analysis tables), qualified references will be included to establish transparent data lineage.

The project will apply several data quality assurance measures: calibration of instruments and imaging systems prior to data acquisition, use of validated protocols for experiments and environmental simulation, consistency checks between datasets and documentation, peer-review of code/scripts used in data analysis, version control of files and clear labelling of file types and revisions.

In line with the broader FAIR principles, the project also addresses outputs beyond datasets. Scientific publications will be deposited in open access, and code or scripts developed for data analysis will be shared under open-source licenses. Data security during the project is ensured through regular backups and institutional storage infrastructure. No personal or sensitive data are processed, and no ethical approvals are required, as all data originate from non-invasive experimental setups and public dissemination activities.

The project allocates the necessary resources—both technical and human—to support good data management throughout its lifecycle, with dedicated support from the hosting institution (Université de Bordeaux) and external infrastructure partners.

3. Other research outputs

- **In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).**
- **Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.**

In addition to research data, the TaphArt project will generate a number of other research outputs, primarily in digital form. These include data analysis scripts, image processing workflows, experimental protocols, and documentation for laboratory simulations related to environmental degradation processes. While the project does not produce software or physical outputs (such as biological samples or new materials), the digital research objects created will be managed according to the same FAIR principles as datasets.

All scripts and workflows developed for processing 3D images, hyperspectral data, or numerical analysis (e.g. statistical comparisons, time-series modeling) will be documented, versioned, and made openly available in open-source repositories such as Zenodo. These will include clear descriptions of dependencies, usage instructions, licensing terms (e.g. MIT or GPL), and links to example datasets when appropriate. Protocols for the experimental simulation of taphonomic processes will be provided as standalone documents (e.g. PDF or Markdown) and will be deposited alongside the datasets they support.

Metadata for these research outputs will include references to related datasets, the project's funding information (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101109977), and licensing conditions, ensuring they are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs) will be assigned to ensure long-term accessibility and citability. Where appropriate, qualified references to external standards or existing methods (e.g. those published in scientific literature or in public repositories like protocols.io) will also be included.

By managing these outputs transparently and openly, the project ensures that not only the data, but the entire analytical and experimental workflow, is reproducible and reusable by the research community—both during and beyond the project lifetime.

4. Allocation of resources

- **What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?**
- **How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)**
- **Who will be responsible for data management in your project?**
- **How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?**

Costs related to making data and other research outputs FAIR in the TaphArt project are limited but accounted for. They primarily include indirect costs associated with the time needed to document, prepare, and curate datasets, scripts, and protocols for open access deposition; as well as minor direct costs related to long-term storage and archiving in trusted repositories. No external data management service providers are involved.

These efforts are covered by personnel costs already budgeted in the project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) framework. This includes time allocated by the fellow for preparing data and metadata, documenting experimental workflows, and depositing outputs in repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala. The hosting institution, Université de Bordeaux, also provides in-kind support via its Research Data service and access to Huma-Num infrastructure for deposit in Nakala. These resources fall under eligible costs according to the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement.

The person responsible for data management is the MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow (Neemias Santos da Rosa), with support from the Université de Bordeaux Research Data Officer and technical assistance from the institutional IT and research support services.

Long-term preservation will be ensured through the selection of trusted, EOSC-compatible repositories that commit to multi-year storage and persistent access, such as Zenodo, Nakala, or a suitable ARIADNEplus node. These platforms ensure at least 10 years of data availability, with metadata guaranteed to remain available even if the datasets are withdrawn or archived.

The datasets to be preserved long-term include:

- All experimental datasets (raw and processed)
- Associated metadata and documentation
- Analysis scripts and protocols

The decision on what to retain is made by the fellow in coordination with the supervisor and based on the scientific value, potential for reuse, and compliance with Horizon Europe's open science guidelines. No significant financial investment is foreseen for long-term preservation, as the repositories selected offer free or publicly funded services for open-access projects. However, additional backup copies will be maintained on the institution's internal research data servers to provide redundancy and safeguard research integrity.

5. Data security

- **What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?**
- **Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?**

All research data generated during the TaphArt project will be managed using secure and reliable infrastructure provided by the Université de Bordeaux, which ensures compliance with institutional and European standards for data security. During the active phase of the project, data will be stored on institutional servers with regular automated backups, version control, and access-restricted folders when appropriate. In addition, data are also stored locally on encrypted, access-controlled devices used by the researcher, with periodic manual backups to secure drives.

Although the project does not involve sensitive or personal data, all files are handled with care to prevent loss, corruption, or

unauthorized modification. No transfer of confidential or ethically regulated content is expected.

Once validated and prepared for publication, datasets will be transferred to trusted repositories for long-term preservation. These include Zenodo, Nakala (operated by Huma-Num), and possibly a disciplinary repository within ARIADNEplus, all of which guarantee secure storage, open access compliance, and persistent identifiers. These platforms ensure redundant storage, data integrity, and metadata preservation, meeting the requirements for Horizon Europe-funded projects.

The selected repositories are aligned with FAIR principles and provide the technical infrastructure necessary for long-term curation and data recovery. As a result, data security is ensured both during the project and after its completion, supporting sustainable and open research practices.

6. Ethics

- **Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).**
- **Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?**

There are no ethics or legal issues that impact data sharing in the TaphArt project. The research does not involve the collection or processing of personal data, nor does it include any data subject to ethical review (such as human participants, sensitive materials, or restricted cultural heritage content). All experimental procedures involve non-invasive analysis of materials created by the research team, and all dissemination materials (e.g. photographs or videos of outreach events) involve only project members or public audiences in open settings, with no collection of identifiable information.

As such, no informed consent for data sharing or preservation is required, and no personal or sensitive data are included in any dataset generated. This has been clearly stated in the ethics self-assessment submitted during the proposal phase, and confirmed in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethics deliverables are expected for this project, and the data management strategy fully complies with the legal and ethical framework of Horizon Europe, as well as the institutional policies of the Université de Bordeaux.

Should any unforeseen ethical or legal concerns arise (e.g. third-party copyright in dissemination materials), they will be addressed by applying appropriate licensing restrictions or access limitations, and by documenting these conditions transparently in the dataset metadata.

7. Other issues

- **Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?**

In addition to complying with Horizon Europe requirements and the FAIR principles, the TaphArt project also follows national and institutional procedures for data management:

- **Université de Bordeaux Research Data Policy:** The project aligns with the institutional guidelines on responsible research data management, as outlined by the Université de Bordeaux. This includes the use of secure storage infrastructure, good documentation practices, and the recommendation to deposit data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala (Huma-Num).
- **Huma-Num (TGIR) infrastructure:** As a project based in France and hosted by a public research institution, TaphArt has access to the national humanities data infrastructure Huma-Num, which provides long-term preservation services via Nakala, along with guidance on metadata and licensing. Use of Huma-Num services ensures alignment with French national recommendations on open science and digital humanities.
- **Open Science recommendations by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research:** The project contributes to the broader implementation of the French National Plan for Open Science, which promotes free access to research data, interoperability, and reusability, particularly for publicly funded research.

These procedures complement the Horizon Europe open science framework and help ensure the sustainability, legality, and reusability of the research outputs during and after the project.

Photographs of experimental rock art paintings before, during, and after degradation experiments

1. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The dataset "EXP_DEGR_PHOTO" consists of high-resolution photographs taken before, during, and after the experimental degradation of painted rock art surfaces. The data is entirely original and generated within the TaphArt project. No pre-existing datasets are reused, as the photographic documentation specifically reflects the experimental conditions and time-based changes produced during this unique study.

Images are captured in RAW and JPG formats, with an estimated total data volume of approximately 120 GB. The purpose of this dataset is to visually record the progressive deterioration of the painted surfaces subjected to simulated taphonomic processes, notably wind erosion and marine aerosol exposure. These visual records are essential for tracking changes in surface texture, color, and pigment distribution over time, and for correlating them with analytical measurements.

The data is produced in controlled laboratory environments at the Université de Bordeaux, UPV/EHU, and the German Aerospace Center. It provides a detailed visual chronology of the degradation phenomena under investigation and will contribute to the development of a predictive model for the survival of prehistoric rock art under similar environmental pressures. The dataset will be valuable to archaeologists, materials scientists, conservation specialists, and scholars interested in the long-term preservation of cultural heritage in coastal and semi-arid environments.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

All datasets generated by the TaphArt project will be assigned a persistent identifier (DOI) upon deposit, ensuring stable and long-term accessibility. The primary repository foreseen is Zenodo, which automatically assigns DOIs and complies with OpenAIRE guidelines. In parallel, the project is exploring the use of Nakala, the French trusted repository operated by TGIR Huma-Num, which also supports DOI assignment through DataCite and offers long-term preservation on national infrastructure.

For datasets with high disciplinary value in archaeology (e.g. experimental imaging, geochemical analyses, context-specific datasets), the project will evaluate the possibility of depositing through a national node of ARIADNEplus, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS, UK) or DANS (Netherlands), depending on suitability and institutional agreements.

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Keywords will be systematically provided to support discovery and reuse, with particular attention to terms relevant to Middle Stone Age archaeology, experimental rock art degradation, imaging techniques, and conservation science.

All metadata will be published openly and structured in machine-readable formats, ensuring compatibility with standard harvesting protocols such as OAI-PMH. This will enable indexing by OpenAIRE, EOSC, and other aggregators, guaranteeing that datasets are discoverable by both human users and automated services.

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2.2.2. Making data accessible : Data

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- **If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.**
- **Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?**
- **If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?**
- **How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?**
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An embargo period may be applied in selected cases to allow for the preparation and submission of peer-reviewed publications. In such cases, data will be made openly available at the time of submission of the related publication, in accordance with the project's data sharing policy. Embargo periods, if any, will not exceed six months from the time of data generation, and each dataset record will clearly indicate its availability date.

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Since all data are intended to be open access and no personal or sensitive data are processed, no restrictions on access are foreseen during or after the project. If exceptional access limitations arise (e.g. embargo, third-party copyright), the repository's access control features will be used to temporarily restrict access while providing appropriate metadata and contact information for users seeking early access.

The identity of users accessing the data will not be tracked, as the datasets will be fully open and do not require login or authentication. Download metrics may be collected by the repositories for statistical purposes only.

There is no need for a data access committee, as none of the datasets involve sensitive, personal, or ethically regulated content requiring evaluation of access requests.

2.2.3. Making data accessible : Metadata

- **Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?**
- **How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?**
- **Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**

All metadata associated with the datasets produced by the TaphArt project will be made openly available and published under the CC0 public domain dedication, in compliance with the requirements of the Grant Agreement. This will allow for automatic indexing by platforms such as OpenAIRE and integration into disciplinary catalogues. Each metadata record will include a persistent identifier (DOI) and complete information enabling direct access to the corresponding dataset.

The metadata will include all necessary elements to facilitate access to and reuse of the datasets: title, authors, date, file formats, licensing terms, access protocol, storage location, embargo period (if applicable), and direct links to downloadable files.

All metadata records will explicitly indicate that the dataset was produced under the Horizon Europe TaphArt project (Grant Agreement No. 101109977), ensuring compliance with funder requirements and enabling automatic linkage via OpenAIRE.

The data will be preserved for a minimum of ten years, in accordance with European best practices and the retention policies of the selected repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or an ARIADNEplus node). Even in the event that a dataset must be withdrawn, the corresponding metadata record will remain available as a tombstone page, maintaining citation integrity and reference continuity.

The project does not develop software as a standalone research product, but scripts and data processing code will be produced as part of the data analysis workflow. These scripts (e.g. for image processing, data normalization, or statistical comparison) will be shared alongside the relevant datasets under open-source licenses such as MIT or GPL, and will be deposited in Zenodo, with persistent links included in the associated metadata records.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- **What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?**
- **In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?**
- **Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?**

The TaphArt project will ensure data interoperability by using well-established data formats, disciplinary metadata standards, and community-endorsed best practices. All datasets will be formatted in widely used and open formats such as CSV, XLSX, TIFF, JPG, RAW, MP4, ENVI, and HDF5, ensuring compatibility across platforms and disciplines.

Metadata will be structured using the DataCite schema (for Zenodo and Nakala) and, where appropriate, aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM), which is the community-endorsed standard for archaeological datasets. The ACDM provides semantic consistency and facilitates integration into broader infrastructures such as ARIADNEplus, OpenAIRE, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). For tabular and numerical data, standard variable naming and unit conventions will be followed to maximize readability and compatibility.

In case the project generates project-specific vocabularies or uses non-standard terminologies (for instance, for experimental categories or environmental simulation parameters), a mapping to common ontologies will be provided when possible. These vocabularies or classifications will be openly published to enable reuse, refinement, and extension by other researchers.

Where relevant, datasets will include qualified references to other datasets produced within the project (e.g. linking image files to corresponding numerical analysis outputs) or to external datasets used as comparative baselines. These links will be established using persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs or URIs) and clearly described in the metadata to enable structured cross-referencing and semantic interoperability.

The project team is committed to following interoperability best practices promoted by the FAIR principles, including the use of machine-readable formats, standardized variable names, and clear licensing and provenance declarations.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- **How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?**
- **Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data**

- **be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?**
- **Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?**
- **Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?**
- **Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.**
- **Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.**

To ensure maximum data re-use, the TaphArt project will provide comprehensive documentation alongside each dataset. This will include structured README files detailing the methodology, data collection context, file structure, variable definitions, units of measurement, software requirements (if applicable), and any data cleaning or transformation procedures applied. For numerical datasets, codebooks and examples of analytical workflows will be included. For imaging and video datasets, metadata will indicate acquisition parameters, equipment used, and pre/post-processing steps. All documentation will be in English and structured to support understanding and reuse by both domain experts and interdisciplinary users.

All datasets will be made freely available in the public domain under standard open licenses that permit broad reuse. The default license will be CC BY 4.0, unless there is a specific need to apply CC0 (for metadata or non-attributable content) or another recognized license. This licensing approach complies with the obligations set out in the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and ensures legal clarity for data reuse.

The datasets will be structured and documented in such a way that they remain usable by third parties, including after the project ends. Persistent identifiers (DOIs) will be assigned to all datasets, and hosting in trusted repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus) will guarantee their long-term availability and accessibility, typically for at least 10 years.

Provenance will be fully documented using accepted metadata standards (e.g. DataCite, ACDM), indicating the origin of the data, institutions and researchers involved, instruments or software used, and processing history. When datasets derive from previous project outputs (e.g. linking raw image data to post-processed files or analysis tables), qualified references will be included to establish transparent data lineage.

The project will apply several data quality assurance measures: calibration of instruments and imaging systems prior to data acquisition, use of validated protocols for experiments and environmental simulation, consistency checks between datasets and documentation, peer-review of code/scripts used in data analysis, version control of files and clear labelling of file types and revisions.

In line with the broader FAIR principles, the project also addresses outputs beyond datasets. Scientific publications will be deposited in open access, and code or scripts developed for data analysis will be shared under open-source licenses. Data security during the project is ensured through regular backups and institutional storage infrastructure. No personal or sensitive data are processed, and no ethical approvals are required, as all data originate from non-invasive experimental setups and public dissemination activities.

The project allocates the necessary resources—both technical and human—to support good data management throughout its lifecycle, with dedicated support from the hosting institution (Université de Bordeaux) and external infrastructure partners.

3. Other research outputs

- **In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).**
- **Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.**

In addition to research data, the TaphArt project will generate a number of other research outputs, primarily in digital form. These include data analysis scripts, image processing workflows, experimental protocols, and documentation for laboratory simulations related to environmental degradation processes. While the project does not produce software or physical outputs (such as biological samples or new materials), the digital research objects created will be managed according to the same FAIR principles as datasets.

All scripts and workflows developed for processing 3D images, hyperspectral data, or numerical analysis (e.g. statistical comparisons, time-series modeling) will be documented, versioned, and made openly available in open-source repositories such as Zenodo. These will include clear descriptions of dependencies, usage instructions, licensing terms (e.g. MIT or GPL), and links to example datasets when appropriate. Protocols for the experimental simulation of taphonomic processes will be provided as standalone documents (e.g. PDF or Markdown) and will be deposited alongside the datasets they support.

Metadata for these research outputs will include references to related datasets, the project's funding information (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101109977), and licensing conditions, ensuring they are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs) will be assigned to ensure long-term accessibility and citability. Where appropriate, qualified references to external standards or existing methods (e.g. those published in scientific literature or in public repositories like

protocols.io) will also be included.

By managing these outputs transparently and openly, the project ensures that not only the data, but the entire analytical and experimental workflow, is reproducible and reusable by the research community—both during and beyond the project lifetime.

4. Allocation of resources

- **What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?**
- **How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)**
- **Who will be responsible for data management in your project?**
- **How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?**

Costs related to making data and other research outputs FAIR in the TaphArt project are limited but accounted for. They primarily include indirect costs associated with the time needed to document, prepare, and curate datasets, scripts, and protocols for open access deposition; as well as minor direct costs related to long-term storage and archiving in trusted repositories. No external data management service providers are involved.

These efforts are covered by personnel costs already budgeted in the project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) framework. This includes time allocated by the fellow for preparing data and metadata, documenting experimental workflows, and depositing outputs in repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala. The hosting institution, Université de Bordeaux, also provides in-kind support via its Research Data service and access to Huma-Num infrastructure for deposit in Nakala. These resources fall under eligible costs according to the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement.

The person responsible for data management is the MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow (Neemias Santos da Rosa), with support from the Université de Bordeaux Research Data Officer and technical assistance from the institutional IT and research support services.

Long-term preservation will be ensured through the selection of trusted, EOSC-compatible repositories that commit to multi-year storage and persistent access, such as Zenodo, Nakala, or a suitable ARIADNEplus node. These platforms ensure at least 10 years of data availability, with metadata guaranteed to remain available even if the datasets are withdrawn or archived.

The datasets to be preserved long-term include:

- All experimental datasets (raw and processed)
- Associated metadata and documentation
- Analysis scripts and protocols

The decision on what to retain is made by the fellow in coordination with the supervisor and based on the scientific value, potential for reuse, and compliance with Horizon Europe's open science guidelines. No significant financial investment is foreseen for long-term preservation, as the repositories selected offer free or publicly funded services for open-access projects. However, additional backup copies will be maintained on the institution's internal research data servers to provide redundancy and safeguard research integrity.

5. Data security

- **What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?**
- **Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?**

All research data generated during the TaphArt project will be managed using secure and reliable infrastructure provided by the Université de Bordeaux, which ensures compliance with institutional and European standards for data security. During the active phase of the project, data will be stored on institutional servers with regular automated backups, version control, and access-restricted folders when appropriate. In addition, data are also stored locally on encrypted, access-controlled devices used by the researcher, with periodic manual backups to secure drives.

Although the project does not involve sensitive or personal data, all files are handled with care to prevent loss, corruption, or unauthorized modification. No transfer of confidential or ethically regulated content is expected.

Once validated and prepared for publication, datasets will be transferred to trusted repositories for long-term preservation. These include Zenodo, Nakala (operated by Huma-Num), and possibly a disciplinary repository within ARIADNEplus, all of which

guarantee secure storage, open access compliance, and persistent identifiers. These platforms ensure redundant storage, data integrity, and metadata preservation, meeting the requirements for Horizon Europe-funded projects.

The selected repositories are aligned with FAIR principles and provide the technical infrastructure necessary for long-term curation and data recovery. As a result, data security is ensured both during the project and after its completion, supporting sustainable and open research practices.

6. Ethics

- **Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).**
- **Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?**

There are no ethics or legal issues that impact data sharing in the TaphArt project. The research does not involve the collection or processing of personal data, nor does it include any data subject to ethical review (such as human participants, sensitive materials, or restricted cultural heritage content). All experimental procedures involve non-invasive analysis of materials created by the research team, and all dissemination materials (e.g. photographs or videos of outreach events) involve only project members or public audiences in open settings, with no collection of identifiable information.

As such, no informed consent for data sharing or preservation is required, and no personal or sensitive data are included in any dataset generated. This has been clearly stated in the ethics self-assessment submitted during the proposal phase, and confirmed in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethics deliverables are expected for this project, and the data management strategy fully complies with the legal and ethical framework of Horizon Europe, as well as the institutional policies of the Université de Bordeaux.

Should any unforeseen ethical or legal concerns arise (e.g. third-party copyright in dissemination materials), they will be addressed by applying appropriate licensing restrictions or access limitations, and by documenting these conditions transparently in the dataset metadata.

7. Other issues

- **Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?**

In addition to complying with Horizon Europe requirements and the FAIR principles, the TaphArt project also follows national and institutional procedures for data management:

- **Université de Bordeaux Research Data Policy:** The project aligns with the institutional guidelines on responsible research data management, as outlined by the Université de Bordeaux. This includes the use of secure storage infrastructure, good documentation practices, and the recommendation to deposit data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala (Huma-Num).
- **Huma-Num (TGIR) infrastructure:** As a project based in France and hosted by a public research institution, TaphArt has access to the national humanities data infrastructure Huma-Num, which provides long-term preservation services via Nakala, along with guidance on metadata and licensing. Use of Huma-Num services ensures alignment with French national recommendations on open science and digital humanities.
- **Open Science recommendations by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research:** The project contributes to the broader implementation of the French National Plan for Open Science, which promotes free access to research data, interoperability, and reusability, particularly for publicly funded research.

These procedures complement the Horizon Europe open science framework and help ensure the sustainability, legality, and reusability of the research outputs during and after the project.

3D microscope images of experimental rock art paintings taken during degradation experiments

1. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The dataset "CONF\MICRO\IMG" contains confocal microscope images of experimental rock art paintings captured before, during, and after exposure to simulated taphonomic processes. The data is newly generated for the purposes of the TaphArt project, with no reuse of pre-existing datasets, as the experimental procedures and their microscopic documentation are unique to this study.

The images are saved in TIFF and JPG formats, offering both raw and compressed versions suitable for detailed analysis and broader dissemination. The expected size of the dataset is approximately 80 GB. The main objective of generating this data is to observe and record surface alterations at the microscopic level, enabling the assessment of pigment loss, microstructural degradation, and erosion patterns caused by wind and marine aerosol.

These data are generated in laboratory conditions using confocal microscopy equipment available at the participating research institutions, including the Université de Bordeaux and the University of the Basque Country. The dataset is instrumental for validating visual observations and enhancing the scientific understanding of microscale deterioration processes. It will be of use to specialists in rock art analysis, microscopy, conservation science, and any research area involving pigment stability and surface material characterization under environmental stress.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

All datasets generated by the TaphArt project will be assigned a persistent identifier (DOI) upon deposit, ensuring stable and long-term accessibility. The primary repository foreseen is Zenodo, which automatically assigns DOIs and complies with OpenAIRE guidelines. In parallel, the project is exploring the use of Nakala, the French trusted repository operated by TGIR Huma-Num, which also supports DOI assignment through DataCite and offers long-term preservation on national infrastructure.

For datasets with high disciplinary value in archaeology (e.g. experimental imaging, geochemical analyses, context-specific datasets), the project will evaluate the possibility of depositing through a national node of ARIADNEplus, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS, UK) or DANS (Netherlands), depending on suitability and institutional agreements.

Rich metadata will be created for all datasets, including descriptive elements such as title, authorship, institutional affiliation, abstract, keywords, date and location of data collection, methodology, file formats, licensing, and funding references. Metadata will comply with the DataCite schema (Zenodo and Nakala) and, where applicable, will be aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM) for archaeological content. This ensures semantic interoperability and integration into disciplinary and general discovery platforms.

Keywords will be systematically provided to support discovery and reuse, with particular attention to terms relevant to Middle Stone Age archaeology, experimental rock art degradation, imaging techniques, and conservation science.

All metadata will be published openly and structured in machine-readable formats, ensuring compatibility with standard harvesting protocols such as OAI-PMH. This will enable indexing by OpenAIRE, EOSC, and other aggregators, guaranteeing that datasets are discoverable by both human users and automated services.

2.2.1. Making data accessible : Repository

- **Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?**
- **Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?**
- **Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?**

TaphArt datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories that meet the requirements for FAIR data, long-term accessibility, and OpenAIRE compliance. The primary repository chosen is Zenodo, maintained by CERN and supported by the European Commission. Zenodo is widely used by Horizon Europe projects, ensures robust infrastructure, immediate open access, and automatic DOI assignment.

In addition, the project will consider depositing in Nakala, the national repository for humanities and social sciences operated by TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS). Nakala is a certified repository based in France, providing stable hosting, persistent identifiers (via DataCite), and disciplinary support for research outputs in archaeology and cultural heritage.

For datasets of high archaeological relevance, especially those intended for international reuse or integration in heritage infrastructures, the project will evaluate deposition through the ARIADNEplus infrastructure via an appropriate national node, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) or DANS. This option will be prioritized for datasets that benefit from enriched archaeological metadata and curation.

Exploratory steps have been taken to review the submission procedures, metadata requirements, and licensing conditions for Zenodo and Nakala. The project team is also initiating contacts with ARIADNEplus nodes to assess the feasibility of deposition. All repositories under consideration ensure that datasets are assigned a DOI, which is a persistent and resolvable identifier linking directly to the dataset landing page, enabling durable access and citation.

2.2.2. Making data accessible : Data

- **Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.**
- **If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.**
- **Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?**
- **If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?**
- **How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?**
- **Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?**

All data generated by the TaphArt project will be made openly available as a matter of principle, in alignment with Horizon Europe's open science policies and the project's commitment to transparency, reproducibility, and societal impact. No legal, contractual, ethical, or privacy-related constraints apply to the datasets produced, as the project does not involve personal data or commercially sensitive information. All datasets are based on non-invasive experiments, scientific imaging, and dissemination activities involving consenting participants or publicly accessible materials.

An embargo period may be applied in selected cases to allow for the preparation and submission of peer-reviewed publications. In such cases, data will be made openly available at the time of submission of the related publication, in accordance with the project's data sharing policy. Embargo periods, if any, will not exceed six months from the time of data generation, and each dataset record will clearly indicate its availability date.

All data will be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol, such as HTTPS, ensuring open and unrestricted access via the landing page of the repository (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus node). Each dataset will include a persistent and resolvable DOI that points directly to a public record and download options, without the need for user registration or authentication.

Since all data are intended to be open access and no personal or sensitive data are processed, no restrictions on access are foreseen during or after the project. If exceptional access limitations arise (e.g. embargo, third-party copyright), the repository's access control features will be used to temporarily restrict access while providing appropriate metadata and contact information for users seeking early access.

The identity of users accessing the data will not be tracked, as the datasets will be fully open and do not require login or authentication. Download metrics may be collected by the repositories for statistical purposes only.

There is no need for a data access committee, as none of the datasets involve sensitive, personal, or ethically regulated content requiring evaluation of access requests.

2.2.3. Making data accessible : Metadata

- **Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?**
- **How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?**
- **Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**

All metadata associated with the datasets produced by the TaphArt project will be made openly available and published under the CC0 public domain dedication, in compliance with the requirements of the Grant Agreement. This will allow for automatic indexing by platforms such as OpenAIRE and integration into disciplinary catalogues. Each metadata record will include a persistent identifier (DOI) and complete information enabling direct access to the corresponding dataset.

The metadata will include all necessary elements to facilitate access to and reuse of the datasets: title, authors, date, file formats, licensing terms, access protocol, storage location, embargo period (if applicable), and direct links to downloadable files.

All metadata records will explicitly indicate that the dataset was produced under the Horizon Europe TaphArt project (Grant Agreement No. 101109977), ensuring compliance with funder requirements and enabling automatic linkage via OpenAIRE.

The data will be preserved for a minimum of ten years, in accordance with European best practices and the retention policies of the selected repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or an ARIADNEplus node). Even in the event that a dataset must be withdrawn, the corresponding metadata record will remain available as a tombstone page, maintaining citation integrity and reference continuity.

The project does not develop software as a standalone research product, but scripts and data processing code will be produced as part of the data analysis workflow. These scripts (e.g. for image processing, data normalization, or statistical comparison) will be shared alongside the relevant datasets under open-source licenses such as MIT or GPL, and will be deposited in Zenodo, with persistent links included in the associated metadata records.

2.3. Making data interoperable

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- **In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?**
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Where relevant, datasets will include qualified references to other datasets produced within the project (e.g. linking image files to corresponding numerical analysis outputs) or to external datasets used as comparative baselines. These links will be established using persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs or URIs) and clearly described in the metadata to enable structured cross-referencing and semantic interoperability.

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- **be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?**
- **Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?**
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Metadata for these research outputs will include references to related datasets, the project's funding information (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101109977), and licensing conditions, ensuring they are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs) will be assigned to ensure long-term accessibility and citability. Where appropriate, qualified references to external standards or existing methods (e.g. those published in scientific literature or in public repositories like

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Costs related to making data and other research outputs FAIR in the TaphArt project are limited but accounted for. They primarily include indirect costs associated with the time needed to document, prepare, and curate datasets, scripts, and protocols for open access deposition; as well as minor direct costs related to long-term storage and archiving in trusted repositories. No external data management service providers are involved.

These efforts are covered by personnel costs already budgeted in the project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) framework. This includes time allocated by the fellow for preparing data and metadata, documenting experimental workflows, and depositing outputs in repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala. The hosting institution, Université de Bordeaux, also provides in-kind support via its Research Data service and access to Huma-Num infrastructure for deposit in Nakala. These resources fall under eligible costs according to the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement.

The person responsible for data management is the MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow (Neemias Santos da Rosa), with support from the Université de Bordeaux Research Data Officer and technical assistance from the institutional IT and research support services.

Long-term preservation will be ensured through the selection of trusted, EOSC-compatible repositories that commit to multi-year storage and persistent access, such as Zenodo, Nakala, or a suitable ARIADNEplus node. These platforms ensure at least 10 years of data availability, with metadata guaranteed to remain available even if the datasets are withdrawn or archived.

The datasets to be preserved long-term include:

- All experimental datasets (raw and processed)
- Associated metadata and documentation
- Analysis scripts and protocols

The decision on what to retain is made by the fellow in coordination with the supervisor and based on the scientific value, potential for reuse, and compliance with Horizon Europe's open science guidelines. No significant financial investment is foreseen for long-term preservation, as the repositories selected offer free or publicly funded services for open-access projects. However, additional backup copies will be maintained on the institution's internal research data servers to provide redundancy and safeguard research integrity.

5. Data security

- **What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?**
- **Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?**

All research data generated during the TaphArt project will be managed using secure and reliable infrastructure provided by the Université de Bordeaux, which ensures compliance with institutional and European standards for data security. During the active phase of the project, data will be stored on institutional servers with regular automated backups, version control, and access-restricted folders when appropriate. In addition, data are also stored locally on encrypted, access-controlled devices used by the researcher, with periodic manual backups to secure drives.

Although the project does not involve sensitive or personal data, all files are handled with care to prevent loss, corruption, or unauthorized modification. No transfer of confidential or ethically regulated content is expected.

Once validated and prepared for publication, datasets will be transferred to trusted repositories for long-term preservation. These include Zenodo, Nakala (operated by Huma-Num), and possibly a disciplinary repository within ARIADNEplus, all of which

guarantee secure storage, open access compliance, and persistent identifiers. These platforms ensure redundant storage, data integrity, and metadata preservation, meeting the requirements for Horizon Europe-funded projects.

The selected repositories are aligned with FAIR principles and provide the technical infrastructure necessary for long-term curation and data recovery. As a result, data security is ensured both during the project and after its completion, supporting sustainable and open research practices.

6. Ethics

- **Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).**
- **Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?**

There are no ethics or legal issues that impact data sharing in the TaphArt project. The research does not involve the collection or processing of personal data, nor does it include any data subject to ethical review (such as human participants, sensitive materials, or restricted cultural heritage content). All experimental procedures involve non-invasive analysis of materials created by the research team, and all dissemination materials (e.g. photographs or videos of outreach events) involve only project members or public audiences in open settings, with no collection of identifiable information.

As such, no informed consent for data sharing or preservation is required, and no personal or sensitive data are included in any dataset generated. This has been clearly stated in the ethics self-assessment submitted during the proposal phase, and confirmed in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethics deliverables are expected for this project, and the data management strategy fully complies with the legal and ethical framework of Horizon Europe, as well as the institutional policies of the Université de Bordeaux.

Should any unforeseen ethical or legal concerns arise (e.g. third-party copyright in dissemination materials), they will be addressed by applying appropriate licensing restrictions or access limitations, and by documenting these conditions transparently in the dataset metadata.

7. Other issues

- **Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?**

In addition to complying with Horizon Europe requirements and the FAIR principles, the TaphArt project also follows national and institutional procedures for data management:

- **Université de Bordeaux Research Data Policy:** The project aligns with the institutional guidelines on responsible research data management, as outlined by the Université de Bordeaux. This includes the use of secure storage infrastructure, good documentation practices, and the recommendation to deposit data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala (Huma-Num).
- **Huma-Num (TGIR) infrastructure:** As a project based in France and hosted by a public research institution, TaphArt has access to the national humanities data infrastructure Huma-Num, which provides long-term preservation services via Nakala, along with guidance on metadata and licensing. Use of Huma-Num services ensures alignment with French national recommendations on open science and digital humanities.
- **Open Science recommendations by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research:** The project contributes to the broader implementation of the French National Plan for Open Science, which promotes free access to research data, interoperability, and reusability, particularly for publicly funded research.

These procedures complement the Horizon Europe open science framework and help ensure the sustainability, legality, and reusability of the research outputs during and after the project.

Micro EDXRF mapping images of experimental rock art paintings taken during degradation experiments

1. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The dataset "EDXRF_MAP_IMG" includes micro energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence (EDXRF) mapping images of experimental rock art paintings taken at multiple stages: before, during, and after simulated exposure to taphonomic agents. This dataset is entirely original and produced specifically within the TaphArt project framework, with no reuse of existing data.

The images are stored in TIFF and JPG formats and are expected to amount to approximately 60 GB in size. The purpose of this dataset is to provide elemental distribution maps that reveal chemical changes occurring in the painted surfaces due to wind erosion and marine aerosol degradation. These data are essential for understanding pigment stability and the geochemical signatures of deterioration processes.

The images are generated using micro-EDXRF equipment at the partner institutions, notably the University of the Basque Country and the German Aerospace Center. This dataset contributes directly to the project's goal of modeling degradation pathways and helps correlate visual and chemical evidence of surface alteration. The data will be highly valuable to researchers in archaeometry, materials science, and heritage conservation, as well as those developing non-invasive methods for analyzing cultural heritage materials.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

All datasets generated by the TaphArt project will be assigned a persistent identifier (DOI) upon deposit, ensuring stable and long-term accessibility. The primary repository foreseen is Zenodo, which automatically assigns DOIs and complies with OpenAIRE guidelines. In parallel, the project is exploring the use of Nakala, the French trusted repository operated by TGIR Huma-Num, which also supports DOI assignment through DataCite and offers long-term preservation on national infrastructure.

For datasets with high disciplinary value in archaeology (e.g. experimental imaging, geochemical analyses, context-specific datasets), the project will evaluate the possibility of depositing through a national node of ARIADNEplus, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS, UK) or DANS (Netherlands), depending on suitability and institutional agreements.

Rich metadata will be created for all datasets, including descriptive elements such as title, authorship, institutional affiliation, abstract, keywords, date and location of data collection, methodology, file formats, licensing, and funding references. Metadata will comply with the DataCite schema (Zenodo and Nakala) and, where applicable, will be aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM) for archaeological content. This ensures semantic interoperability and integration into disciplinary and general discovery platforms.

Keywords will be systematically provided to support discovery and reuse, with particular attention to terms relevant to Middle Stone Age archaeology, experimental rock art degradation, imaging techniques, and conservation science.

All metadata will be published openly and structured in machine-readable formats, ensuring compatibility with standard harvesting protocols such as OAI-PMH. This will enable indexing by OpenAIRE, EOSC, and other aggregators, guaranteeing that datasets are discoverable by both human users and automated services.

2.2.1. Making data accessible : Repository

- **Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?**
- **Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?**
- **Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?**

TaphArt datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories that meet the requirements for FAIR data, long-term accessibility, and OpenAIRE compliance. The primary repository chosen is Zenodo, maintained by CERN and supported by the European Commission. Zenodo is widely used by Horizon Europe projects, ensures robust infrastructure, immediate open access, and automatic DOI assignment.

In addition, the project will consider depositing in Nakala, the national repository for humanities and social sciences operated by TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS). Nakala is a certified repository based in France, providing stable hosting, persistent identifiers (via DataCite), and disciplinary support for research outputs in archaeology and cultural heritage.

For datasets of high archaeological relevance, especially those intended for international reuse or integration in heritage infrastructures, the project will evaluate deposition through the ARIADNEplus infrastructure via an appropriate national node, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) or DANS. This option will be prioritized for datasets that benefit from enriched archaeological metadata and curation.

Exploratory steps have been taken to review the submission procedures, metadata requirements, and licensing conditions for Zenodo and Nakala. The project team is also initiating contacts with ARIADNEplus nodes to assess the feasibility of deposition. All repositories under consideration ensure that datasets are assigned a DOI, which is a persistent and resolvable identifier linking directly to the dataset landing page, enabling durable access and citation.

2.2.2. Making data accessible : Data

- **Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.**
- **If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.**
- **Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?**
- **If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?**
- **How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?**
- **Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?**

All data generated by the TaphArt project will be made openly available as a matter of principle, in alignment with Horizon Europe's open science policies and the project's commitment to transparency, reproducibility, and societal impact. No legal, contractual, ethical, or privacy-related constraints apply to the datasets produced, as the project does not involve personal data or commercially sensitive information. All datasets are based on non-invasive experiments, scientific imaging, and dissemination activities involving consenting participants or publicly accessible materials.

An embargo period may be applied in selected cases to allow for the preparation and submission of peer-reviewed publications. In such cases, data will be made openly available at the time of submission of the related publication, in accordance with the project's data sharing policy. Embargo periods, if any, will not exceed six months from the time of data generation, and each dataset record will clearly indicate its availability date.

All data will be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol, such as HTTPS, ensuring open and unrestricted access via the landing page of the repository (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus node). Each dataset will include a persistent and resolvable DOI that points directly to a public record and download options, without the need for user registration or authentication.

Since all data are intended to be open access and no personal or sensitive data are processed, no restrictions on access are foreseen during or after the project. If exceptional access limitations arise (e.g. embargo, third-party copyright), the repository's access control features will be used to temporarily restrict access while providing appropriate metadata and contact information for users seeking early access.

The identity of users accessing the data will not be tracked, as the datasets will be fully open and do not require login or authentication. Download metrics may be collected by the repositories for statistical purposes only.

There is no need for a data access committee, as none of the datasets involve sensitive, personal, or ethically regulated content requiring evaluation of access requests.

2.2.3. Making data accessible : Metadata

- **Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?**
- **How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?**
- **Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**

All metadata associated with the datasets produced by the TaphArt project will be made openly available and published under the CC0 public domain dedication, in compliance with the requirements of the Grant Agreement. This will allow for automatic indexing by platforms such as OpenAIRE and integration into disciplinary catalogues. Each metadata record will include a persistent identifier (DOI) and complete information enabling direct access to the corresponding dataset.

The metadata will include all necessary elements to facilitate access to and reuse of the datasets: title, authors, date, file formats, licensing terms, access protocol, storage location, embargo period (if applicable), and direct links to downloadable files.

All metadata records will explicitly indicate that the dataset was produced under the Horizon Europe TaphArt project (Grant Agreement No. 101109977), ensuring compliance with funder requirements and enabling automatic linkage via OpenAIRE.

The data will be preserved for a minimum of ten years, in accordance with European best practices and the retention policies of the selected repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or an ARIADNEplus node). Even in the event that a dataset must be withdrawn, the corresponding metadata record will remain available as a tombstone page, maintaining citation integrity and reference continuity.

The project does not develop software as a standalone research product, but scripts and data processing code will be produced as part of the data analysis workflow. These scripts (e.g. for image processing, data normalization, or statistical comparison) will be shared alongside the relevant datasets under open-source licenses such as MIT or GPL, and will be deposited in Zenodo, with persistent links included in the associated metadata records.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- **What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?**
- **In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?**
- **Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?**

The TaphArt project will ensure data interoperability by using well-established data formats, disciplinary metadata standards, and community-endorsed best practices. All datasets will be formatted in widely used and open formats such as CSV, XLSX, TIFF, JPG, RAW, MP4, ENVI, and HDF5, ensuring compatibility across platforms and disciplines.

Metadata will be structured using the DataCite schema (for Zenodo and Nakala) and, where appropriate, aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM), which is the community-endorsed standard for archaeological datasets. The ACDM provides semantic consistency and facilitates integration into broader infrastructures such as ARIADNEplus, OpenAIRE, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). For tabular and numerical data, standard variable naming and unit conventions will be followed to maximize readability and compatibility.

In case the project generates project-specific vocabularies or uses non-standard terminologies (for instance, for experimental categories or environmental simulation parameters), a mapping to common ontologies will be provided when possible. These vocabularies or classifications will be openly published to enable reuse, refinement, and extension by other researchers.

Where relevant, datasets will include qualified references to other datasets produced within the project (e.g. linking image files to corresponding numerical analysis outputs) or to external datasets used as comparative baselines. These links will be established using persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs or URIs) and clearly described in the metadata to enable structured cross-referencing and semantic interoperability.

The project team is committed to following interoperability best practices promoted by the FAIR principles, including the use of machine-readable formats, standardized variable names, and clear licensing and provenance declarations.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- **How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?**
- **Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?**
- **Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?**

- **Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?**
- **Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.**
- **Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.**

To ensure maximum data re-use, the TaphArt project will provide comprehensive documentation alongside each dataset. This will include structured README files detailing the methodology, data collection context, file structure, variable definitions, units of measurement, software requirements (if applicable), and any data cleaning or transformation procedures applied. For numerical datasets, codebooks and examples of analytical workflows will be included. For imaging and video datasets, metadata will indicate acquisition parameters, equipment used, and pre/post-processing steps. All documentation will be in English and structured to support understanding and reuse by both domain experts and interdisciplinary users.

All datasets will be made freely available in the public domain under standard open licenses that permit broad reuse. The default license will be CC BY 4.0, unless there is a specific need to apply CC0 (for metadata or non-attributable content) or another recognized license. This licensing approach complies with the obligations set out in the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and ensures legal clarity for data reuse.

The datasets will be structured and documented in such a way that they remain usable by third parties, including after the project ends. Persistent identifiers (DOIs) will be assigned to all datasets, and hosting in trusted repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus) will guarantee their long-term availability and accessibility, typically for at least 10 years.

Provenance will be fully documented using accepted metadata standards (e.g. DataCite, ACDM), indicating the origin of the data, institutions and researchers involved, instruments or software used, and processing history. When datasets derive from previous project outputs (e.g. linking raw image data to post-processed files or analysis tables), qualified references will be included to establish transparent data lineage.

The project will apply several data quality assurance measures: calibration of instruments and imaging systems prior to data acquisition, use of validated protocols for experiments and environmental simulation, consistency checks between datasets and documentation, peer-review of code/scripts used in data analysis, version control of files and clear labelling of file types and revisions.

In line with the broader FAIR principles, the project also addresses outputs beyond datasets. Scientific publications will be deposited in open access, and code or scripts developed for data analysis will be shared under open-source licenses. Data security during the project is ensured through regular backups and institutional storage infrastructure. No personal or sensitive data are processed, and no ethical approvals are required, as all data originate from non-invasive experimental setups and public dissemination activities.

The project allocates the necessary resources—both technical and human—to support good data management throughout its lifecycle, with dedicated support from the hosting institution (Université de Bordeaux) and external infrastructure partners.

3. Other research outputs

- **In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).**
- **Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.**

In addition to research data, the TaphArt project will generate a number of other research outputs, primarily in digital form. These include data analysis scripts, image processing workflows, experimental protocols, and documentation for laboratory simulations related to environmental degradation processes. While the project does not produce software or physical outputs (such as biological samples or new materials), the digital research objects created will be managed according to the same FAIR principles as datasets.

All scripts and workflows developed for processing 3D images, hyperspectral data, or numerical analysis (e.g. statistical comparisons, time-series modeling) will be documented, versioned, and made openly available in open-source repositories such as Zenodo. These will include clear descriptions of dependencies, usage instructions, licensing terms (e.g. MIT or GPL), and links to example datasets when appropriate. Protocols for the experimental simulation of taphonomic processes will be provided as standalone documents (e.g. PDF or Markdown) and will be deposited alongside the datasets they support.

Metadata for these research outputs will include references to related datasets, the project's funding information (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101109977), and licensing conditions, ensuring they are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs) will be assigned to ensure long-term accessibility and citability. Where appropriate, qualified references to external standards or existing methods (e.g. those published in scientific literature or in public repositories like protocols.io) will also be included.

By managing these outputs transparently and openly, the project ensures that not only the data, but the entire analytical and

experimental workflow, is reproducible and reusable by the research community—both during and beyond the project lifetime.

4. Allocation of resources

- **What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?**
- **How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)**
- **Who will be responsible for data management in your project?**
- **How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?**

Costs related to making data and other research outputs FAIR in the TaphArt project are limited but accounted for. They primarily include indirect costs associated with the time needed to document, prepare, and curate datasets, scripts, and protocols for open access deposition; as well as minor direct costs related to long-term storage and archiving in trusted repositories. No external data management service providers are involved.

These efforts are covered by personnel costs already budgeted in the project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) framework. This includes time allocated by the fellow for preparing data and metadata, documenting experimental workflows, and depositing outputs in repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala. The hosting institution, Université de Bordeaux, also provides in-kind support via its Research Data service and access to Huma-Num infrastructure for deposit in Nakala. These resources fall under eligible costs according to the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement.

The person responsible for data management is the MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow (Neemias Santos da Rosa), with support from the Université de Bordeaux Research Data Officer and technical assistance from the institutional IT and research support services.

Long-term preservation will be ensured through the selection of trusted, EOSC-compatible repositories that commit to multi-year storage and persistent access, such as Zenodo, Nakala, or a suitable ARIADNEplus node. These platforms ensure at least 10 years of data availability, with metadata guaranteed to remain available even if the datasets are withdrawn or archived.

The datasets to be preserved long-term include:

- All experimental datasets (raw and processed)
- Associated metadata and documentation
- Analysis scripts and protocols

The decision on what to retain is made by the fellow in coordination with the supervisor and based on the scientific value, potential for reuse, and compliance with Horizon Europe's open science guidelines. No significant financial investment is foreseen for long-term preservation, as the repositories selected offer free or publicly funded services for open-access projects. However, additional backup copies will be maintained on the institution's internal research data servers to provide redundancy and safeguard research integrity.

5. Data security

- **What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?**
- **Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?**

All research data generated during the TaphArt project will be managed using secure and reliable infrastructure provided by the Université de Bordeaux, which ensures compliance with institutional and European standards for data security. During the active phase of the project, data will be stored on institutional servers with regular automated backups, version control, and access-restricted folders when appropriate. In addition, data are also stored locally on encrypted, access-controlled devices used by the researcher, with periodic manual backups to secure drives.

Although the project does not involve sensitive or personal data, all files are handled with care to prevent loss, corruption, or unauthorized modification. No transfer of confidential or ethically regulated content is expected.

Once validated and prepared for publication, datasets will be transferred to trusted repositories for long-term preservation. These include Zenodo, Nakala (operated by Huma-Num), and possibly a disciplinary repository within ARIADNEplus, all of which guarantee secure storage, open access compliance, and persistent identifiers. These platforms ensure redundant storage, data integrity, and metadata preservation, meeting the requirements for Horizon Europe-funded projects.

The selected repositories are aligned with FAIR principles and provide the technical infrastructure necessary for long-term curation and data recovery. As a result, data security is ensured both during the project and after its completion, supporting sustainable and open research practices.

6. Ethics

- **Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).**
- **Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?**

There are no ethics or legal issues that impact data sharing in the TaphArt project. The research does not involve the collection or processing of personal data, nor does it include any data subject to ethical review (such as human participants, sensitive materials, or restricted cultural heritage content). All experimental procedures involve non-invasive analysis of materials created by the research team, and all dissemination materials (e.g. photographs or videos of outreach events) involve only project members or public audiences in open settings, with no collection of identifiable information.

As such, no informed consent for data sharing or preservation is required, and no personal or sensitive data are included in any dataset generated. This has been clearly stated in the ethics self-assessment submitted during the proposal phase, and confirmed in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethics deliverables are expected for this project, and the data management strategy fully complies with the legal and ethical framework of Horizon Europe, as well as the institutional policies of the Université de Bordeaux.

Should any unforeseen ethical or legal concerns arise (e.g. third-party copyright in dissemination materials), they will be addressed by applying appropriate licensing restrictions or access limitations, and by documenting these conditions transparently in the dataset metadata.

7. Other issues

- **Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?**

In addition to complying with Horizon Europe requirements and the FAIR principles, the TaphArt project also follows national and institutional procedures for data management:

- **Université de Bordeaux Research Data Policy:** The project aligns with the institutional guidelines on responsible research data management, as outlined by the Université de Bordeaux. This includes the use of secure storage infrastructure, good documentation practices, and the recommendation to deposit data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala (Huma-Num).
- **Huma-Num (TGIR) infrastructure:** As a project based in France and hosted by a public research institution, TaphArt has access to the national humanities data infrastructure Huma-Num, which provides long-term preservation services via Nakala, along with guidance on metadata and licensing. Use of Huma-Num services ensures alignment with French national recommendations on open science and digital humanities.
- **Open Science recommendations by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research:** The project contributes to the broader implementation of the French National Plan for Open Science, which promotes free access to research data, interoperability, and reusability, particularly for publicly funded research.

These procedures complement the Horizon Europe open science framework and help ensure the sustainability, legality, and reusability of the research outputs during and after the project.

Hyperspectral images of experimental rock art paintings taken during degradation experiments

1. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The dataset "HYPERSP_IMG" consists of hyperspectral images of experimental rock art paintings acquired before, during, and after exposure to simulated taphonomic conditions. All data is newly generated within the TaphArt project; no existing data is reused, as the spectral imaging is specifically tailored to the experimental protocols developed for this research.

The dataset will be provided in ENVI and HDF5 formats and is expected to reach approximately 200 GB, due to the high spectral and spatial resolution of the images. The objective of this dataset is to detect and quantify subtle changes in surface composition and pigment reflectance across the visible and near-infrared spectrum. This spectral information supports the identification of degradation markers that are not visible through conventional imaging.

Data acquisition takes place in laboratory settings, primarily at the German Aerospace Center, using calibrated hyperspectral imaging systems. The dataset plays a critical role in the project's aim to develop a predictive model for pigment survival and to assess the impact of environmental factors on the visibility and persistence of prehistoric painted imagery. It will be of significant interest to researchers in remote sensing, rock art conservation, imaging science, and archaeological documentation.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

All datasets generated by the TaphArt project will be assigned a persistent identifier (DOI) upon deposit, ensuring stable and long-term accessibility. The primary repository foreseen is Zenodo, which automatically assigns DOIs and complies with OpenAIRE guidelines. In parallel, the project is exploring the use of Nakala, the French trusted repository operated by TGIR Huma-Num, which also supports DOI assignment through DataCite and offers long-term preservation on national infrastructure.

For datasets with high disciplinary value in archaeology (e.g. experimental imaging, geochemical analyses, context-specific datasets), the project will evaluate the possibility of depositing through a national node of ARIADNEplus, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS, UK) or DANS (Netherlands), depending on suitability and institutional agreements.

Rich metadata will be created for all datasets, including descriptive elements such as title, authorship, institutional affiliation, abstract, keywords, date and location of data collection, methodology, file formats, licensing, and funding references. Metadata will comply with the DataCite schema (Zenodo and Nakala) and, where applicable, will be aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM) for archaeological content. This ensures semantic interoperability and integration into disciplinary and general discovery platforms.

Keywords will be systematically provided to support discovery and reuse, with particular attention to terms relevant to Middle Stone Age archaeology, experimental rock art degradation, imaging techniques, and conservation science.

All metadata will be published openly and structured in machine-readable formats, ensuring compatibility with standard harvesting protocols such as OAI-PMH. This will enable indexing by OpenAIRE, EOSC, and other aggregators, guaranteeing that datasets are discoverable by both human users and automated services.

2.2.1. Making data accessible : Repository

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

- **Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?**
- **Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?**

TaphArt datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories that meet the requirements for FAIR data, long-term accessibility, and OpenAIRE compliance. The primary repository chosen is Zenodo, maintained by CERN and supported by the European Commission. Zenodo is widely used by Horizon Europe projects, ensures robust infrastructure, immediate open access, and automatic DOI assignment.

In addition, the project will consider depositing in Nakala, the national repository for humanities and social sciences operated by TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS). Nakala is a certified repository based in France, providing stable hosting, persistent identifiers (via DataCite), and disciplinary support for research outputs in archaeology and cultural heritage.

For datasets of high archaeological relevance, especially those intended for international reuse or integration in heritage infrastructures, the project will evaluate deposition through the ARIADNEplus infrastructure via an appropriate national node, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) or DANS. This option will be prioritized for datasets that benefit from enriched archaeological metadata and curation.

Exploratory steps have been taken to review the submission procedures, metadata requirements, and licensing conditions for Zenodo and Nakala. The project team is also initiating contacts with ARIADNEplus nodes to assess the feasibility of deposition. All repositories under consideration ensure that datasets are assigned a DOI, which is a persistent and resolvable identifier linking directly to the dataset landing page, enabling durable access and citation.

2.2.2. Making data accessible : Data

- **Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.**
- **If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.**
- **Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?**
- **If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?**
- **How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?**
- **Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?**

All data generated by the TaphArt project will be made openly available as a matter of principle, in alignment with Horizon Europe's open science policies and the project's commitment to transparency, reproducibility, and societal impact. No legal, contractual, ethical, or privacy-related constraints apply to the datasets produced, as the project does not involve personal data or commercially sensitive information. All datasets are based on non-invasive experiments, scientific imaging, and dissemination activities involving consenting participants or publicly accessible materials.

An embargo period may be applied in selected cases to allow for the preparation and submission of peer-reviewed publications. In such cases, data will be made openly available at the time of submission of the related publication, in accordance with the project's data sharing policy. Embargo periods, if any, will not exceed six months from the time of data generation, and each dataset record will clearly indicate its availability date.

All data will be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol, such as HTTPS, ensuring open and unrestricted access via the landing page of the repository (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus node). Each dataset will include a persistent and resolvable DOI that points directly to a public record and download options, without the need for user registration or authentication.

Since all data are intended to be open access and no personal or sensitive data are processed, no restrictions on access are foreseen during or after the project. If exceptional access limitations arise (e.g. embargo, third-party copyright), the repository's access control features will be used to temporarily restrict access while providing appropriate metadata and contact information for users seeking early access.

The identity of users accessing the data will not be tracked, as the datasets will be fully open and do not require login or authentication. Download metrics may be collected by the repositories for statistical purposes only.

There is no need for a data access committee, as none of the datasets involve sensitive, personal, or ethically regulated content requiring evaluation of access requests.

2.2.3. Making data accessible : Metadata

- **Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?**

- **How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?**
- **Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**

All metadata associated with the datasets produced by the TaphArt project will be made openly available and published under the CC0 public domain dedication, in compliance with the requirements of the Grant Agreement. This will allow for automatic indexing by platforms such as OpenAIRE and integration into disciplinary catalogues. Each metadata record will include a persistent identifier (DOI) and complete information enabling direct access to the corresponding dataset.

The metadata will include all necessary elements to facilitate access to and reuse of the datasets: title, authors, date, file formats, licensing terms, access protocol, storage location, embargo period (if applicable), and direct links to downloadable files.

All metadata records will explicitly indicate that the dataset was produced under the Horizon Europe TaphArt project (Grant Agreement No. 101109977), ensuring compliance with funder requirements and enabling automatic linkage via OpenAIRE.

The data will be preserved for a minimum of ten years, in accordance with European best practices and the retention policies of the selected repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or an ARIADNEplus node). Even in the event that a dataset must be withdrawn, the corresponding metadata record will remain available as a tombstone page, maintaining citation integrity and reference continuity.

The project does not develop software as a standalone research product, but scripts and data processing code will be produced as part of the data analysis workflow. These scripts (e.g. for image processing, data normalization, or statistical comparison) will be shared alongside the relevant datasets under open-source licenses such as MIT or GPL, and will be deposited in Zenodo, with persistent links included in the associated metadata records.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- **What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?**
- **In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?**
- **Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?**

The TaphArt project will ensure data interoperability by using well-established data formats, disciplinary metadata standards, and community-endorsed best practices. All datasets will be formatted in widely used and open formats such as CSV, XLSX, TIFF, JPG, RAW, MP4, ENVI, and HDF5, ensuring compatibility across platforms and disciplines.

Metadata will be structured using the DataCite schema (for Zenodo and Nakala) and, where appropriate, aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM), which is the community-endorsed standard for archaeological datasets. The ACDM provides semantic consistency and facilitates integration into broader infrastructures such as ARIADNEplus, OpenAIRE, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). For tabular and numerical data, standard variable naming and unit conventions will be followed to maximize readability and compatibility.

In case the project generates project-specific vocabularies or uses non-standard terminologies (for instance, for experimental categories or environmental simulation parameters), a mapping to common ontologies will be provided when possible. These vocabularies or classifications will be openly published to enable reuse, refinement, and extension by other researchers.

Where relevant, datasets will include qualified references to other datasets produced within the project (e.g. linking image files to corresponding numerical analysis outputs) or to external datasets used as comparative baselines. These links will be established using persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs or URIs) and clearly described in the metadata to enable structured cross-referencing and semantic interoperability.

The project team is committed to following interoperability best practices promoted by the FAIR principles, including the use of machine-readable formats, standardized variable names, and clear licensing and provenance declarations.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- **How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?**
- **Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?**
- **Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?**
- **Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?**
- **Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.**
- **Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.**

To ensure maximum data re-use, the TaphArt project will provide comprehensive documentation alongside each dataset. This will include structured README files detailing the methodology, data collection context, file structure, variable definitions, units of measurement, software requirements (if applicable), and any data cleaning or transformation procedures applied. For numerical datasets, codebooks and examples of analytical workflows will be included. For imaging and video datasets, metadata will indicate acquisition parameters, equipment used, and pre/post-processing steps. All documentation will be in English and structured to support understanding and reuse by both domain experts and interdisciplinary users.

All datasets will be made freely available in the public domain under standard open licenses that permit broad reuse. The default license will be CC BY 4.0, unless there is a specific need to apply CC0 (for metadata or non-attributable content) or another recognized license. This licensing approach complies with the obligations set out in the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and ensures legal clarity for data reuse.

The datasets will be structured and documented in such a way that they remain usable by third parties, including after the project ends. Persistent identifiers (DOIs) will be assigned to all datasets, and hosting in trusted repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus) will guarantee their long-term availability and accessibility, typically for at least 10 years.

Provenance will be fully documented using accepted metadata standards (e.g. DataCite, ACDM), indicating the origin of the data, institutions and researchers involved, instruments or software used, and processing history. When datasets derive from previous project outputs (e.g. linking raw image data to post-processed files or analysis tables), qualified references will be included to establish transparent data lineage.

The project will apply several data quality assurance measures: calibration of instruments and imaging systems prior to data acquisition, use of validated protocols for experiments and environmental simulation, consistency checks between datasets and documentation, peer-review of code/scripts used in data analysis, version control of files and clear labelling of file types and revisions.

In line with the broader FAIR principles, the project also addresses outputs beyond datasets. Scientific publications will be deposited in open access, and code or scripts developed for data analysis will be shared under open-source licenses. Data security during the project is ensured through regular backups and institutional storage infrastructure. No personal or sensitive data are processed, and no ethical approvals are required, as all data originate from non-invasive experimental setups and public dissemination activities.

The project allocates the necessary resources—both technical and human—to support good data management throughout its lifecycle, with dedicated support from the hosting institution (Université de Bordeaux) and external infrastructure partners.

3. Other research outputs

- **In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).**
- **Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.**

In addition to research data, the TaphArt project will generate a number of other research outputs, primarily in digital form. These include data analysis scripts, image processing workflows, experimental protocols, and documentation for laboratory simulations related to environmental degradation processes. While the project does not produce software or physical outputs (such as biological samples or new materials), the digital research objects created will be managed according to the same FAIR principles as datasets.

All scripts and workflows developed for processing 3D images, hyperspectral data, or numerical analysis (e.g. statistical comparisons, time-series modeling) will be documented, versioned, and made openly available in open-source repositories such as Zenodo. These will include clear descriptions of dependencies, usage instructions, licensing terms (e.g. MIT or GPL), and links to example datasets when appropriate. Protocols for the experimental simulation of taphonomic processes will be provided as standalone documents (e.g. PDF or Markdown) and will be deposited alongside the datasets they support.

Metadata for these research outputs will include references to related datasets, the project's funding information (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101109977), and licensing conditions, ensuring they are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs) will be assigned to ensure long-term accessibility and citability. Where appropriate, qualified references to external standards or existing methods (e.g. those published in scientific literature or in public repositories like protocols.io) will also be included.

By managing these outputs transparently and openly, the project ensures that not only the data, but the entire analytical and experimental workflow, is reproducible and reusable by the research community—both during and beyond the project lifetime.

4. Allocation of resources

- **What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?**
- **How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)**
- **Who will be responsible for data management in your project?**
- **How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?**

Costs related to making data and other research outputs FAIR in the TaphArt project are limited but accounted for. They primarily include indirect costs associated with the time needed to document, prepare, and curate datasets, scripts, and protocols for open access deposition; as well as minor direct costs related to long-term storage and archiving in trusted repositories. No external data management service providers are involved.

These efforts are covered by personnel costs already budgeted in the project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) framework. This includes time allocated by the fellow for preparing data and metadata, documenting experimental workflows, and depositing outputs in repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala. The hosting institution, Université de Bordeaux, also provides in-kind support via its Research Data service and access to Huma-Num infrastructure for deposit in Nakala. These resources fall under eligible costs according to the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement.

The person responsible for data management is the MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow (Neemias Santos da Rosa), with support from the Université de Bordeaux Research Data Officer and technical assistance from the institutional IT and research support services.

Long-term preservation will be ensured through the selection of trusted, EOSC-compatible repositories that commit to multi-year storage and persistent access, such as Zenodo, Nakala, or a suitable ARIADNEplus node. These platforms ensure at least 10 years of data availability, with metadata guaranteed to remain available even if the datasets are withdrawn or archived.

The datasets to be preserved long-term include:

- All experimental datasets (raw and processed)
- Associated metadata and documentation
- Analysis scripts and protocols

The decision on what to retain is made by the fellow in coordination with the supervisor and based on the scientific value, potential for reuse, and compliance with Horizon Europe's open science guidelines. No significant financial investment is foreseen for long-term preservation, as the repositories selected offer free or publicly funded services for open-access projects. However, additional backup copies will be maintained on the institution's internal research data servers to provide redundancy and safeguard research integrity.

5. Data security

- **What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?**
- **Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?**

All research data generated during the TaphArt project will be managed using secure and reliable infrastructure provided by the Université de Bordeaux, which ensures compliance with institutional and European standards for data security. During the active phase of the project, data will be stored on institutional servers with regular automated backups, version control, and access-restricted folders when appropriate. In addition, data are also stored locally on encrypted, access-controlled devices used by the researcher, with periodic manual backups to secure drives.

Although the project does not involve sensitive or personal data, all files are handled with care to prevent loss, corruption, or unauthorized modification. No transfer of confidential or ethically regulated content is expected.

Once validated and prepared for publication, datasets will be transferred to trusted repositories for long-term preservation. These include Zenodo, Nakala (operated by Huma-Num), and possibly a disciplinary repository within ARIADNEplus, all of which guarantee secure storage, open access compliance, and persistent identifiers. These platforms ensure redundant storage, data integrity, and metadata preservation, meeting the requirements for Horizon Europe-funded projects.

The selected repositories are aligned with FAIR principles and provide the technical infrastructure necessary for long-term curation and data recovery. As a result, data security is ensured both during the project and after its completion, supporting sustainable and open research practices.

6. Ethics

- **Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).**
- **Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?**

There are no ethics or legal issues that impact data sharing in the TaphArt project. The research does not involve the collection or processing of personal data, nor does it include any data subject to ethical review (such as human participants, sensitive materials, or restricted cultural heritage content). All experimental procedures involve non-invasive analysis of materials created by the research team, and all dissemination materials (e.g. photographs or videos of outreach events) involve only project members or public audiences in open settings, with no collection of identifiable information.

As such, no informed consent for data sharing or preservation is required, and no personal or sensitive data are included in any dataset generated. This has been clearly stated in the ethics self-assessment submitted during the proposal phase, and confirmed in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethics deliverables are expected for this project, and the data management strategy fully complies with the legal and ethical framework of Horizon Europe, as well as the institutional policies of the Université de Bordeaux.

Should any unforeseen ethical or legal concerns arise (e.g. third-party copyright in dissemination materials), they will be addressed by applying appropriate licensing restrictions or access limitations, and by documenting these conditions transparently in the dataset metadata.

7. Other issues

- **Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?**

In addition to complying with Horizon Europe requirements and the FAIR principles, the TaphArt project also follows national and institutional procedures for data management:

- **Université de Bordeaux Research Data Policy:** The project aligns with the institutional guidelines on responsible research data management, as outlined by the Université de Bordeaux. This includes the use of secure storage infrastructure, good documentation practices, and the recommendation to deposit data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala (Huma-Num).
- **Huma-Num (TGIR) infrastructure:** As a project based in France and hosted by a public research institution, TaphArt has access to the national humanities data infrastructure Huma-Num, which provides long-term preservation services via Nakala, along with guidance on metadata and licensing. Use of Huma-Num services ensures alignment with French national recommendations on open science and digital humanities.
- **Open Science recommendations by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research:** The project contributes to the broader implementation of the French National Plan for Open Science, which promotes free access to research data, interoperability, and reusability, particularly for publicly funded research.

These procedures complement the Horizon Europe open science framework and help ensure the sustainability, legality, and reusability of the research outputs during and after the project.

Numerical data from analysis using 3D microscopy, micro EDXRF mapping and hyperspectral imaging

1. Data Summary

- **Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.**
- **What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?**
- **What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?**
- **What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?**
- **What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?**
- **To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?**

The dataset "ANALYSIS_NUMDATA" contains numerical data derived from the analysis of confocal microscopy, micro EDXRF mapping, and hyperspectral imaging performed on experimental rock art samples. This dataset is entirely original and produced as part of the TaphArt project, with no reuse of existing datasets, since all measurements correspond to new experimental conditions designed to simulate specific taphonomic processes.

The data is stored in CSV and XLSX formats and is expected to total approximately 20 GB. It includes quantitative variables such as intensity values, spectral reflectance indices, elemental concentrations, and surface profile measurements. The dataset is essential for conducting comparative analysis across the different imaging modalities and for supporting the development of an integrated model of surface degradation.

This data is generated by the research team using specialized analytical software and instruments at the Université de Bordeaux, the University of the Basque Country, and the German Aerospace Center. It provides the numerical foundation for interpreting visual and chemical alterations observed in the experimental samples. The dataset will be particularly useful to researchers engaged in data-driven heritage science, archaeometry, environmental modeling, and predictive analysis in conservation research.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- **Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?**
- **Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.**
- **Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?**
- **Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?**

All datasets generated by the TaphArt project will be assigned a persistent identifier (DOI) upon deposit, ensuring stable and long-term accessibility. The primary repository foreseen is Zenodo, which automatically assigns DOIs and complies with OpenAIRE guidelines. In parallel, the project is exploring the use of Nakala, the French trusted repository operated by TGIR Huma-Num, which also supports DOI assignment through DataCite and offers long-term preservation on national infrastructure.

For datasets with high disciplinary value in archaeology (e.g. experimental imaging, geochemical analyses, context-specific datasets), the project will evaluate the possibility of depositing through a national node of ARIADNEplus, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS, UK) or DANS (Netherlands), depending on suitability and institutional agreements.

Rich metadata will be created for all datasets, including descriptive elements such as title, authorship, institutional affiliation, abstract, keywords, date and location of data collection, methodology, file formats, licensing, and funding references. Metadata will comply with the DataCite schema (Zenodo and Nakala) and, where applicable, will be aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM) for archaeological content. This ensures semantic interoperability and integration into disciplinary and general discovery platforms.

Keywords will be systematically provided to support discovery and reuse, with particular attention to terms relevant to Middle Stone Age archaeology, experimental rock art degradation, imaging techniques, and conservation science.

All metadata will be published openly and structured in machine-readable formats, ensuring compatibility with standard harvesting protocols such as OAI-PMH. This will enable indexing by OpenAIRE, EOSC, and other aggregators, guaranteeing that datasets are discoverable by both human users and automated services.

2.2.1. Making data accessible : Repository

- **Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?**
- **Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?**
- **Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?**

TaphArt datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories that meet the requirements for FAIR data, long-term accessibility, and OpenAIRE compliance. The primary repository chosen is Zenodo, maintained by CERN and supported by the European Commission. Zenodo is widely used by Horizon Europe projects, ensures robust infrastructure, immediate open access, and automatic DOI assignment.

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For datasets of high archaeological relevance, especially those intended for international reuse or integration in heritage infrastructures, the project will evaluate deposition through the ARIADNEplus infrastructure via an appropriate national node, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) or DANS. This option will be prioritized for datasets that benefit from enriched archaeological metadata and curation.

Exploratory steps have been taken to review the submission procedures, metadata requirements, and licensing conditions for Zenodo and Nakala. The project team is also initiating contacts with ARIADNEplus nodes to assess the feasibility of deposition. All repositories under consideration ensure that datasets are assigned a DOI, which is a persistent and resolvable identifier linking directly to the dataset landing page, enabling durable access and citation.

2.2.2. Making data accessible : Data

- **Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.**
- **If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.**
- **Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?**
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An embargo period may be applied in selected cases to allow for the preparation and submission of peer-reviewed publications. In such cases, data will be made openly available at the time of submission of the related publication, in accordance with the project's data sharing policy. Embargo periods, if any, will not exceed six months from the time of data generation, and each dataset record will clearly indicate its availability date.

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Since all data are intended to be open access and no personal or sensitive data are processed, no restrictions on access are foreseen during or after the project. If exceptional access limitations arise (e.g. embargo, third-party copyright), the repository's access control features will be used to temporarily restrict access while providing appropriate metadata and contact information for users seeking early access.

The identity of users accessing the data will not be tracked, as the datasets will be fully open and do not require login or authentication. Download metrics may be collected by the repositories for statistical purposes only.

There is no need for a data access committee, as none of the datasets involve sensitive, personal, or ethically regulated content requiring evaluation of access requests.

2.2.3. Making data accessible : Metadata

- **Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?**
- **How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?**
- **Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**

All metadata associated with the datasets produced by the TaphArt project will be made openly available and published under the CC0 public domain dedication, in compliance with the requirements of the Grant Agreement. This will allow for automatic indexing by platforms such as OpenAIRE and integration into disciplinary catalogues. Each metadata record will include a persistent identifier (DOI) and complete information enabling direct access to the corresponding dataset.

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All metadata records will explicitly indicate that the dataset was produced under the Horizon Europe TaphArt project (Grant Agreement No. 101109977), ensuring compliance with funder requirements and enabling automatic linkage via OpenAIRE.

The data will be preserved for a minimum of ten years, in accordance with European best practices and the retention policies of the selected repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or an ARIADNEplus node). Even in the event that a dataset must be withdrawn, the corresponding metadata record will remain available as a tombstone page, maintaining citation integrity and reference continuity.

The project does not develop software as a standalone research product, but scripts and data processing code will be produced as part of the data analysis workflow. These scripts (e.g. for image processing, data normalization, or statistical comparison) will be shared alongside the relevant datasets under open-source licenses such as MIT or GPL, and will be deposited in Zenodo, with persistent links included in the associated metadata records.

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Metadata will be structured using the DataCite schema (for Zenodo and Nakala) and, where appropriate, aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM), which is the community-endorsed standard for archaeological datasets. The ACDM provides semantic consistency and facilitates integration into broader infrastructures such as ARIADNEplus, OpenAIRE, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). For tabular and numerical data, standard variable naming and unit conventions will be followed to maximize readability and compatibility.

In case the project generates project-specific vocabularies or uses non-standard terminologies (for instance, for experimental categories or environmental simulation parameters), a mapping to common ontologies will be provided when possible. These vocabularies or classifications will be openly published to enable reuse, refinement, and extension by other researchers.

Where relevant, datasets will include qualified references to other datasets produced within the project (e.g. linking image files to corresponding numerical analysis outputs) or to external datasets used as comparative baselines. These links will be established using persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs or URIs) and clearly described in the metadata to enable structured cross-referencing and semantic interoperability.

The project team is committed to following interoperability best practices promoted by the FAIR principles, including the use of machine-readable formats, standardized variable names, and clear licensing and provenance declarations.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- **How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?**
- **Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?**
- **Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?**
- **Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?**
- **Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.**
- **Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.**

To ensure maximum data re-use, the TaphArt project will provide comprehensive documentation alongside each dataset. This will

include structured README files detailing the methodology, data collection context, file structure, variable definitions, units of measurement, software requirements (if applicable), and any data cleaning or transformation procedures applied. For numerical datasets, codebooks and examples of analytical workflows will be included. For imaging and video datasets, metadata will indicate acquisition parameters, equipment used, and pre/post-processing steps. All documentation will be in English and structured to support understanding and reuse by both domain experts and interdisciplinary users.

All datasets will be made freely available in the public domain under standard open licenses that permit broad reuse. The default license will be CC BY 4.0, unless there is a specific need to apply CC0 (for metadata or non-attributable content) or another recognized license. This licensing approach complies with the obligations set out in the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and ensures legal clarity for data reuse.

The datasets will be structured and documented in such a way that they remain usable by third parties, including after the project ends. Persistent identifiers (DOIs) will be assigned to all datasets, and hosting in trusted repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus) will guarantee their long-term availability and accessibility, typically for at least 10 years.

Provenance will be fully documented using accepted metadata standards (e.g. DataCite, ACDM), indicating the origin of the data, institutions and researchers involved, instruments or software used, and processing history. When datasets derive from previous project outputs (e.g. linking raw image data to post-processed files or analysis tables), qualified references will be included to establish transparent data lineage.

The project will apply several data quality assurance measures: calibration of instruments and imaging systems prior to data acquisition, use of validated protocols for experiments and environmental simulation, consistency checks between datasets and documentation, peer-review of code/scripts used in data analysis, version control of files and clear labelling of file types and revisions.

In line with the broader FAIR principles, the project also addresses outputs beyond datasets. Scientific publications will be deposited in open access, and code or scripts developed for data analysis will be shared under open-source licenses. Data security during the project is ensured through regular backups and institutional storage infrastructure. No personal or sensitive data are processed, and no ethical approvals are required, as all data originate from non-invasive experimental setups and public dissemination activities.

The project allocates the necessary resources—both technical and human—to support good data management throughout its lifecycle, with dedicated support from the hosting institution (Université de Bordeaux) and external infrastructure partners.

3. Other research outputs

- **In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).**
- **Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.**

In addition to research data, the TaphArt project will generate a number of other research outputs, primarily in digital form. These include data analysis scripts, image processing workflows, experimental protocols, and documentation for laboratory simulations related to environmental degradation processes. While the project does not produce software or physical outputs (such as biological samples or new materials), the digital research objects created will be managed according to the same FAIR principles as datasets.

All scripts and workflows developed for processing 3D images, hyperspectral data, or numerical analysis (e.g. statistical comparisons, time-series modeling) will be documented, versioned, and made openly available in open-source repositories such as Zenodo. These will include clear descriptions of dependencies, usage instructions, licensing terms (e.g. MIT or GPL), and links to example datasets when appropriate. Protocols for the experimental simulation of taphonomic processes will be provided as standalone documents (e.g. PDF or Markdown) and will be deposited alongside the datasets they support.

Metadata for these research outputs will include references to related datasets, the project's funding information (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101109977), and licensing conditions, ensuring they are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs) will be assigned to ensure long-term accessibility and citability. Where appropriate, qualified references to external standards or existing methods (e.g. those published in scientific literature or in public repositories like protocols.io) will also be included.

By managing these outputs transparently and openly, the project ensures that not only the data, but the entire analytical and experimental workflow, is reproducible and reusable by the research community—both during and beyond the project lifetime.

4. Allocation of resources

- **What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?**
- **How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)**
- **Who will be responsible for data management in your project?**
- **How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?**

Costs related to making data and other research outputs FAIR in the TaphArt project are limited but accounted for. They primarily include indirect costs associated with the time needed to document, prepare, and curate datasets, scripts, and protocols for open access deposition; as well as minor direct costs related to long-term storage and archiving in trusted repositories. No external data management service providers are involved.

These efforts are covered by personnel costs already budgeted in the project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) framework. This includes time allocated by the fellow for preparing data and metadata, documenting experimental workflows, and depositing outputs in repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala. The hosting institution, Université de Bordeaux, also provides in-kind support via its Research Data service and access to Huma-Num infrastructure for deposit in Nakala. These resources fall under eligible costs according to the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement.

The person responsible for data management is the MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow (Neemias Santos da Rosa), with support from the Université de Bordeaux Research Data Officer and technical assistance from the institutional IT and research support services.

Long-term preservation will be ensured through the selection of trusted, EOSC-compatible repositories that commit to multi-year storage and persistent access, such as Zenodo, Nakala, or a suitable ARIADNEplus node. These platforms ensure at least 10 years of data availability, with metadata guaranteed to remain available even if the datasets are withdrawn or archived.

The datasets to be preserved long-term include:

- All experimental datasets (raw and processed)
- Associated metadata and documentation
- Analysis scripts and protocols

The decision on what to retain is made by the fellow in coordination with the supervisor and based on the scientific value, potential for reuse, and compliance with Horizon Europe's open science guidelines. No significant financial investment is foreseen for long-term preservation, as the repositories selected offer free or publicly funded services for open-access projects. However, additional backup copies will be maintained on the institution's internal research data servers to provide redundancy and safeguard research integrity.

5. Data security

- **What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?**
- **Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?**

All research data generated during the TaphArt project will be managed using secure and reliable infrastructure provided by the Université de Bordeaux, which ensures compliance with institutional and European standards for data security. During the active phase of the project, data will be stored on institutional servers with regular automated backups, version control, and access-restricted folders when appropriate. In addition, data are also stored locally on encrypted, access-controlled devices used by the researcher, with periodic manual backups to secure drives.

Although the project does not involve sensitive or personal data, all files are handled with care to prevent loss, corruption, or unauthorized modification. No transfer of confidential or ethically regulated content is expected.

Once validated and prepared for publication, datasets will be transferred to trusted repositories for long-term preservation. These include Zenodo, Nakala (operated by Huma-Num), and possibly a disciplinary repository within ARIADNEplus, all of which guarantee secure storage, open access compliance, and persistent identifiers. These platforms ensure redundant storage, data integrity, and metadata preservation, meeting the requirements for Horizon Europe-funded projects.

The selected repositories are aligned with FAIR principles and provide the technical infrastructure necessary for long-term curation and data recovery. As a result, data security is ensured both during the project and after its completion, supporting sustainable and open research practices.

6. Ethics

- **Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).**
- **Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?**

There are no ethics or legal issues that impact data sharing in the TaphArt project. The research does not involve the collection or processing of personal data, nor does it include any data subject to ethical review (such as human participants, sensitive materials, or restricted cultural heritage content). All experimental procedures involve non-invasive analysis of materials created by the research team, and all dissemination materials (e.g. photographs or videos of outreach events) involve only project members or public audiences in open settings, with no collection of identifiable information.

As such, no informed consent for data sharing or preservation is required, and no personal or sensitive data are included in any dataset generated. This has been clearly stated in the ethics self-assessment submitted during the proposal phase, and confirmed in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethics deliverables are expected for this project, and the data management strategy fully complies with the legal and ethical framework of Horizon Europe, as well as the institutional policies of the Université de Bordeaux.

Should any unforeseen ethical or legal concerns arise (e.g. third-party copyright in dissemination materials), they will be addressed by applying appropriate licensing restrictions or access limitations, and by documenting these conditions transparently in the dataset metadata.

7. Other issues

- **Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?**

In addition to complying with Horizon Europe requirements and the FAIR principles, the TaphArt project also follows national and institutional procedures for data management:

- **Université de Bordeaux Research Data Policy:** The project aligns with the institutional guidelines on responsible research data management, as outlined by the Université de Bordeaux. This includes the use of secure storage infrastructure, good documentation practices, and the recommendation to deposit data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala (Huma-Num).
- **Huma-Num (TGIR) infrastructure:** As a project based in France and hosted by a public research institution, TaphArt has access to the national humanities data infrastructure Huma-Num, which provides long-term preservation services via Nakala, along with guidance on metadata and licensing. Use of Huma-Num services ensures alignment with French national recommendations on open science and digital humanities.
- **Open Science recommendations by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research:** The project contributes to the broader implementation of the French National Plan for Open Science, which promotes free access to research data, interoperability, and reusability, particularly for publicly funded research.

These procedures complement the Horizon Europe open science framework and help ensure the sustainability, legality, and reusability of the research outputs during and after the project.

Datasets compiling numerical data generated during the experiments

1. Data Summary

- **Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.**
- **What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?**
- **What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?**
- **What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?**

- **What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?**
- **To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?**

The dataset "EXP_DATASETS" compiles all numerical data generated throughout the experimental phase of the TaphArt project. It aggregates results obtained from various analytical methods including confocal microscopy, micro EDXRF mapping, and hyperspectral imaging. The data is entirely new and produced specifically for the project; no existing datasets are reused.

Stored in CSV and XLSX formats, the dataset is expected to reach approximately 25 GB. It includes structured tables and matrices that consolidate processed measurements, temporal comparisons, and quantitative indicators of surface degradation. Its purpose is to serve as the main data resource for statistical analysis, cross-modality interpretation, and model development related to the effects of wind erosion and marine aerosol on painted surfaces.

This integrated dataset is compiled by the research team at the Université de Bordeaux and collaborating institutions, using standardized workflows to ensure coherence and reusability. It plays a central role in validating the experimental protocol and is essential to the predictive framework the project seeks to build. The dataset will be of strong interest to researchers in archaeological science, conservation diagnostics, and those developing interdisciplinary approaches to material degradation under environmental stress.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- **Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?**
- **Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.**
- **Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?**
- **Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?**

All datasets generated by the TaphArt project will be assigned a persistent identifier (DOI) upon deposit, ensuring stable and long-term accessibility. The primary repository foreseen is Zenodo, which automatically assigns DOIs and complies with OpenAIRE guidelines. In parallel, the project is exploring the use of Nakala, the French trusted repository operated by TGIR Huma-Num, which also supports DOI assignment through DataCite and offers long-term preservation on national infrastructure.

For datasets with high disciplinary value in archaeology (e.g. experimental imaging, geochemical analyses, context-specific datasets), the project will evaluate the possibility of depositing through a national node of ARIADNEplus, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS, UK) or DANS (Netherlands), depending on suitability and institutional agreements.

Rich metadata will be created for all datasets, including descriptive elements such as title, authorship, institutional affiliation, abstract, keywords, date and location of data collection, methodology, file formats, licensing, and funding references. Metadata will comply with the DataCite schema (Zenodo and Nakala) and, where applicable, will be aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM) for archaeological content. This ensures semantic interoperability and integration into disciplinary and general discovery platforms.

Keywords will be systematically provided to support discovery and reuse, with particular attention to terms relevant to Middle Stone Age archaeology, experimental rock art degradation, imaging techniques, and conservation science.

All metadata will be published openly and structured in machine-readable formats, ensuring compatibility with standard harvesting protocols such as OAI-PMH. This will enable indexing by OpenAIRE, EOSC, and other aggregators, guaranteeing that datasets are discoverable by both human users and automated services.

2.2.1. Making data accessible : Repository

- **Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?**
- **Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?**
- **Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?**

TaphArt datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories that meet the requirements for FAIR data, long-term accessibility, and OpenAIRE compliance. The primary repository chosen is Zenodo, maintained by CERN and supported by the European Commission. Zenodo is widely used by Horizon Europe projects, ensures robust infrastructure, immediate open access, and automatic DOI assignment.

In addition, the project will consider depositing in Nakala, the national repository for humanities and social sciences operated by TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS). Nakala is a certified repository based in France, providing stable hosting, persistent identifiers (via DataCite), and disciplinary support for research outputs in archaeology and cultural heritage.

For datasets of high archaeological relevance, especially those intended for international reuse or integration in heritage infrastructures, the project will evaluate deposition through the ARIADNEplus infrastructure via an appropriate national node, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) or DANS. This option will be prioritized for datasets that benefit from enriched archaeological metadata and curation.

Exploratory steps have been taken to review the submission procedures, metadata requirements, and licensing conditions for Zenodo and Nakala. The project team is also initiating contacts with ARIADNEplus nodes to assess the feasibility of deposition. All repositories under consideration ensure that datasets are assigned a DOI, which is a persistent and resolvable identifier linking directly to the dataset landing page, enabling durable access and citation.

2.2.2. Making data accessible : Data

- **Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.**
- **If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.**
- **Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?**
- **If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?**
- **How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?**
- **Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?**

All data generated by the TaphArt project will be made openly available as a matter of principle, in alignment with Horizon Europe's open science policies and the project's commitment to transparency, reproducibility, and societal impact. No legal, contractual, ethical, or privacy-related constraints apply to the datasets produced, as the project does not involve personal data or commercially sensitive information. All datasets are based on non-invasive experiments, scientific imaging, and dissemination activities involving consenting participants or publicly accessible materials.

An embargo period may be applied in selected cases to allow for the preparation and submission of peer-reviewed publications. In such cases, data will be made openly available at the time of submission of the related publication, in accordance with the project's data sharing policy. Embargo periods, if any, will not exceed six months from the time of data generation, and each dataset record will clearly indicate its availability date.

All data will be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol, such as HTTPS, ensuring open and unrestricted access via the landing page of the repository (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus node). Each dataset will include a persistent and resolvable DOI that points directly to a public record and download options, without the need for user registration or authentication.

Since all data are intended to be open access and no personal or sensitive data are processed, no restrictions on access are foreseen during or after the project. If exceptional access limitations arise (e.g. embargo, third-party copyright), the repository's access control features will be used to temporarily restrict access while providing appropriate metadata and contact information for users seeking early access.

The identity of users accessing the data will not be tracked, as the datasets will be fully open and do not require login or authentication. Download metrics may be collected by the repositories for statistical purposes only.

There is no need for a data access committee, as none of the datasets involve sensitive, personal, or ethically regulated content requiring evaluation of access requests.

2.2.3. Making data accessible : Metadata

- **Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?**
- **How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?**
- **Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**

All metadata associated with the datasets produced by the TaphArt project will be made openly available and published under the CC0 public domain dedication, in compliance with the requirements of the Grant Agreement. This will allow for automatic indexing by platforms such as OpenAIRE and integration into disciplinary catalogues. Each metadata record will include a persistent

identifier (DOI) and complete information enabling direct access to the corresponding dataset.

The metadata will include all necessary elements to facilitate access to and reuse of the datasets: title, authors, date, file formats, licensing terms, access protocol, storage location, embargo period (if applicable), and direct links to downloadable files.

All metadata records will explicitly indicate that the dataset was produced under the Horizon Europe TaphArt project (Grant Agreement No. 101109977), ensuring compliance with funder requirements and enabling automatic linkage via OpenAIRE.

The data will be preserved for a minimum of ten years, in accordance with European best practices and the retention policies of the selected repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or an ARIADNEplus node). Even in the event that a dataset must be withdrawn, the corresponding metadata record will remain available as a tombstone page, maintaining citation integrity and reference continuity.

The project does not develop software as a standalone research product, but scripts and data processing code will be produced as part of the data analysis workflow. These scripts (e.g. for image processing, data normalization, or statistical comparison) will be shared alongside the relevant datasets under open-source licenses such as MIT or GPL, and will be deposited in Zenodo, with persistent links included in the associated metadata records.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- **What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?**
- **In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?**
- **Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?**

The TaphArt project will ensure data interoperability by using well-established data formats, disciplinary metadata standards, and community-endorsed best practices. All datasets will be formatted in widely used and open formats such as CSV, XLSX, TIFF, JPG, RAW, MP4, ENVI, and HDF5, ensuring compatibility across platforms and disciplines.

Metadata will be structured using the DataCite schema (for Zenodo and Nakala) and, where appropriate, aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM), which is the community-endorsed standard for archaeological datasets. The ACDM provides semantic consistency and facilitates integration into broader infrastructures such as ARIADNEplus, OpenAIRE, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). For tabular and numerical data, standard variable naming and unit conventions will be followed to maximize readability and compatibility.

In case the project generates project-specific vocabularies or uses non-standard terminologies (for instance, for experimental categories or environmental simulation parameters), a mapping to common ontologies will be provided when possible. These vocabularies or classifications will be openly published to enable reuse, refinement, and extension by other researchers.

Where relevant, datasets will include qualified references to other datasets produced within the project (e.g. linking image files to corresponding numerical analysis outputs) or to external datasets used as comparative baselines. These links will be established using persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs or URIs) and clearly described in the metadata to enable structured cross-referencing and semantic interoperability.

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Metadata for these research outputs will include references to related datasets, the project's funding information (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101109977), and licensing conditions, ensuring they are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs) will be assigned to ensure long-term accessibility and citability. Where appropriate, qualified references to external standards or existing methods (e.g. those published in scientific literature or in public repositories like protocols.io) will also be included.

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These efforts are covered by personnel costs already budgeted in the project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) framework. This includes time allocated by the fellow for preparing data and metadata, documenting experimental workflows, and depositing outputs in repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala. The hosting institution, Université de Bordeaux, also provides in-kind support via its Research Data service and access to Huma-Num infrastructure for deposit in Nakala. These resources fall under eligible costs according to the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement.

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All research data generated during the TaphArt project will be managed using secure and reliable infrastructure provided by the Université de Bordeaux, which ensures compliance with institutional and European standards for data security. During the active phase of the project, data will be stored on institutional servers with regular automated backups, version control, and access-restricted folders when appropriate. In addition, data are also stored locally on encrypted, access-controlled devices used by the researcher, with periodic manual backups to secure drives.

Although the project does not involve sensitive or personal data, all files are handled with care to prevent loss, corruption, or unauthorized modification. No transfer of confidential or ethically regulated content is expected.

Once validated and prepared for publication, datasets will be transferred to trusted repositories for long-term preservation. These include Zenodo, Nakala (operated by Huma-Num), and possibly a disciplinary repository within ARIADNEplus, all of which guarantee secure storage, open access compliance, and persistent identifiers. These platforms ensure redundant storage, data integrity, and metadata preservation, meeting the requirements for Horizon Europe-funded projects.

The selected repositories are aligned with FAIR principles and provide the technical infrastructure necessary for long-term curation and data recovery. As a result, data security is ensured both during the project and after its completion, supporting sustainable and open research practices.

6. Ethics

- **Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).**
- **Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with**

personal data?

There are no ethics or legal issues that impact data sharing in the TaphArt project. The research does not involve the collection or processing of personal data, nor does it include any data subject to ethical review (such as human participants, sensitive materials, or restricted cultural heritage content). All experimental procedures involve non-invasive analysis of materials created by the research team, and all dissemination materials (e.g. photographs or videos of outreach events) involve only project members or public audiences in open settings, with no collection of identifiable information.

As such, no informed consent for data sharing or preservation is required, and no personal or sensitive data are included in any dataset generated. This has been clearly stated in the ethics self-assessment submitted during the proposal phase, and confirmed in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethics deliverables are expected for this project, and the data management strategy fully complies with the legal and ethical framework of Horizon Europe, as well as the institutional policies of the Université de Bordeaux.

Should any unforeseen ethical or legal concerns arise (e.g. third-party copyright in dissemination materials), they will be addressed by applying appropriate licensing restrictions or access limitations, and by documenting these conditions transparently in the dataset metadata.

7. Other issues

- **Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?**

In addition to complying with Horizon Europe requirements and the FAIR principles, the TaphArt project also follows national and institutional procedures for data management:

- **Université de Bordeaux Research Data Policy:** The project aligns with the institutional guidelines on responsible research data management, as outlined by the Université de Bordeaux. This includes the use of secure storage infrastructure, good documentation practices, and the recommendation to deposit data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala (Huma-Num).
- **Huma-Num (TGIR) infrastructure:** As a project based in France and hosted by a public research institution, TaphArt has access to the national humanities data infrastructure Huma-Num, which provides long-term preservation services via Nakala, along with guidance on metadata and licensing. Use of Huma-Num services ensures alignment with French national recommendations on open science and digital humanities.
- **Open Science recommendations by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research:** The project contributes to the broader implementation of the French National Plan for Open Science, which promotes free access to research data, interoperability, and reusability, particularly for publicly funded research.

These procedures complement the Horizon Europe open science framework and help ensure the sustainability, legality, and reusability of the research outputs during and after the project.

Project documents (career development plan, DMP, dissemination plan, journal articles, datasets)

1. Data Summary

- **Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.**
- **What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?**
- **What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?**
- **What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?**
- **What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?**
- **To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?**

The dataset "PROJECT_DOCS" includes all documents defined as deliverables within the TaphArt project, such as the Career Development Plan, Data Management Plan, Dissemination Plan, journal articles, and datasets associated with scientific reporting. All documents are created specifically for the project and do not involve the reuse of previous material, although some content may reference or build upon prior research in the literature.

The files are provided in DOC, PDF, and XLSX formats and are expected to represent a relatively small volume of around 2 GB. The purpose of this dataset is to ensure traceability, transparency, and open access to the project's planning, management, and scientific output. These documents are fundamental to fulfilling Horizon Europe requirements for project accountability and open science dissemination.

All documents are produced by the research fellow and project partners, primarily coordinated by the Université de Bordeaux. The dataset supports institutional, funder, and public understanding of the research process and outcomes. It is particularly useful to research managers, future MSCA fellows, science policy analysts, and researchers seeking examples of good practice in project design and reporting within a European framework.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- **Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?**
- **Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.**
- **Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?**
- **Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?**

All datasets generated by the TaphArt project will be assigned a persistent identifier (DOI) upon deposit, ensuring stable and long-term accessibility. The primary repository foreseen is Zenodo, which automatically assigns DOIs and complies with OpenAIRE guidelines. In parallel, the project is exploring the use of Nakala, the French trusted repository operated by TGIR Huma-Num, which also supports DOI assignment through DataCite and offers long-term preservation on national infrastructure.

For datasets with high disciplinary value in archaeology (e.g. experimental imaging, geochemical analyses, context-specific datasets), the project will evaluate the possibility of depositing through a national node of ARIADNEplus, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS, UK) or DANS (Netherlands), depending on suitability and institutional agreements.

Rich metadata will be created for all datasets, including descriptive elements such as title, authorship, institutional affiliation, abstract, keywords, date and location of data collection, methodology, file formats, licensing, and funding references. Metadata will comply with the DataCite schema (Zenodo and Nakala) and, where applicable, will be aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM) for archaeological content. This ensures semantic interoperability and integration into disciplinary and general discovery platforms.

Keywords will be systematically provided to support discovery and reuse, with particular attention to terms relevant to Middle Stone Age archaeology, experimental rock art degradation, imaging techniques, and conservation science.

All metadata will be published openly and structured in machine-readable formats, ensuring compatibility with standard harvesting protocols such as OAI-PMH. This will enable indexing by OpenAIRE, EOSC, and other aggregators, guaranteeing that datasets are discoverable by both human users and automated services.

2.2.1. Making data accessible : Repository

- **Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?**
- **Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?**
- **Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?**

TaphArt datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories that meet the requirements for FAIR data, long-term accessibility, and OpenAIRE compliance. The primary repository chosen is Zenodo, maintained by CERN and supported by the European Commission. Zenodo is widely used by Horizon Europe projects, ensures robust infrastructure, immediate open access, and automatic DOI assignment.

In addition, the project will consider depositing in Nakala, the national repository for humanities and social sciences operated by TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS). Nakala is a certified repository based in France, providing stable hosting, persistent identifiers (via DataCite), and disciplinary support for research outputs in archaeology and cultural heritage.

For datasets of high archaeological relevance, especially those intended for international reuse or integration in heritage infrastructures, the project will evaluate deposition through the ARIADNEplus infrastructure via an appropriate national node,

such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) or DANS. This option will be prioritized for datasets that benefit from enriched archaeological metadata and curation.

Exploratory steps have been taken to review the submission procedures, metadata requirements, and licensing conditions for Zenodo and Nakala. The project team is also initiating contacts with ARIADNEplus nodes to assess the feasibility of deposition. All repositories under consideration ensure that datasets are assigned a DOI, which is a persistent and resolvable identifier linking directly to the dataset landing page, enabling durable access and citation.

2.2.2. Making data accessible : Data

- **Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.**
- **If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.**
- **Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?**
- **If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?**
- **How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?**
- **Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?**

All data generated by the TaphArt project will be made openly available as a matter of principle, in alignment with Horizon Europe's open science policies and the project's commitment to transparency, reproducibility, and societal impact. No legal, contractual, ethical, or privacy-related constraints apply to the datasets produced, as the project does not involve personal data or commercially sensitive information. All datasets are based on non-invasive experiments, scientific imaging, and dissemination activities involving consenting participants or publicly accessible materials.

An embargo period may be applied in selected cases to allow for the preparation and submission of peer-reviewed publications. In such cases, data will be made openly available at the time of submission of the related publication, in accordance with the project's data sharing policy. Embargo periods, if any, will not exceed six months from the time of data generation, and each dataset record will clearly indicate its availability date.

All data will be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol, such as HTTPS, ensuring open and unrestricted access via the landing page of the repository (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus node). Each dataset will include a persistent and resolvable DOI that points directly to a public record and download options, without the need for user registration or authentication.

Since all data are intended to be open access and no personal or sensitive data are processed, no restrictions on access are foreseen during or after the project. If exceptional access limitations arise (e.g. embargo, third-party copyright), the repository's access control features will be used to temporarily restrict access while providing appropriate metadata and contact information for users seeking early access.

The identity of users accessing the data will not be tracked, as the datasets will be fully open and do not require login or authentication. Download metrics may be collected by the repositories for statistical purposes only.

There is no need for a data access committee, as none of the datasets involve sensitive, personal, or ethically regulated content requiring evaluation of access requests.

2.2.3. Making data accessible : Metadata

- **Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?**
- **How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?**
- **Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**

All metadata associated with the datasets produced by the TaphArt project will be made openly available and published under the CC0 public domain dedication, in compliance with the requirements of the Grant Agreement. This will allow for automatic indexing by platforms such as OpenAIRE and integration into disciplinary catalogues. Each metadata record will include a persistent identifier (DOI) and complete information enabling direct access to the corresponding dataset.

The metadata will include all necessary elements to facilitate access to and reuse of the datasets: title, authors, date, file formats, licensing terms, access protocol, storage location, embargo period (if applicable), and direct links to downloadable files.

All metadata records will explicitly indicate that the dataset was produced under the Horizon Europe TaphArt project (Grant Agreement No. 101109977), ensuring compliance with funder requirements and enabling automatic linkage via OpenAIRE.

The data will be preserved for a minimum of ten years, in accordance with European best practices and the retention policies of the selected repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or an ARIADNEplus node). Even in the event that a dataset must be withdrawn, the corresponding metadata record will remain available as a tombstone page, maintaining citation integrity and reference continuity. The project does not develop software as a standalone research product, but scripts and data processing code will be produced as part of the data analysis workflow. These scripts (e.g. for image processing, data normalization, or statistical comparison) will be shared alongside the relevant datasets under open-source licenses such as MIT or GPL, and will be deposited in Zenodo, with persistent links included in the associated metadata records.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- **What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?**
- **In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?**
- **Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?**

The TaphArt project will ensure data interoperability by using well-established data formats, disciplinary metadata standards, and community-endorsed best practices. All datasets will be formatted in widely used and open formats such as CSV, XLSX, TIFF, JPG, RAW, MP4, ENVI, and HDF5, ensuring compatibility across platforms and disciplines.

Metadata will be structured using the DataCite schema (for Zenodo and Nakala) and, where appropriate, aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM), which is the community-endorsed standard for archaeological datasets. The ACDM provides semantic consistency and facilitates integration into broader infrastructures such as ARIADNEplus, OpenAIRE, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). For tabular and numerical data, standard variable naming and unit conventions will be followed to maximize readability and compatibility.

In case the project generates project-specific vocabularies or uses non-standard terminologies (for instance, for experimental categories or environmental simulation parameters), a mapping to common ontologies will be provided when possible. These vocabularies or classifications will be openly published to enable reuse, refinement, and extension by other researchers.

Where relevant, datasets will include qualified references to other datasets produced within the project (e.g. linking image files to corresponding numerical analysis outputs) or to external datasets used as comparative baselines. These links will be established using persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs or URIs) and clearly described in the metadata to enable structured cross-referencing and semantic interoperability.

The project team is committed to following interoperability best practices promoted by the FAIR principles, including the use of machine-readable formats, standardized variable names, and clear licensing and provenance declarations.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- **How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?**
- **Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?**
- **Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?**
- **Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?**
- **Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.**
- **Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.**

To ensure maximum data re-use, the TaphArt project will provide comprehensive documentation alongside each dataset. This will include structured README files detailing the methodology, data collection context, file structure, variable definitions, units of measurement, software requirements (if applicable), and any data cleaning or transformation procedures applied. For numerical datasets, codebooks and examples of analytical workflows will be included. For imaging and video datasets, metadata will indicate acquisition parameters, equipment used, and pre/post-processing steps. All documentation will be in English and structured to support understanding and reuse by both domain experts and interdisciplinary users.

All datasets will be made freely available in the public domain under standard open licenses that permit broad reuse. The default license will be CC BY 4.0, unless there is a specific need to apply CC0 (for metadata or non-attributable content) or another recognized license. This licensing approach complies with the obligations set out in the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and ensures legal clarity for data reuse.

The datasets will be structured and documented in such a way that they remain usable by third parties, including after the project ends. Persistent identifiers (DOIs) will be assigned to all datasets, and hosting in trusted repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or

ARIADNEplus) will guarantee their long-term availability and accessibility, typically for at least 10 years.

Provenance will be fully documented using accepted metadata standards (e.g. DataCite, ACDM), indicating the origin of the data, institutions and researchers involved, instruments or software used, and processing history. When datasets derive from previous project outputs (e.g. linking raw image data to post-processed files or analysis tables), qualified references will be included to establish transparent data lineage.

The project will apply several data quality assurance measures: calibration of instruments and imaging systems prior to data acquisition, use of validated protocols for experiments and environmental simulation, consistency checks between datasets and documentation, peer-review of code/scripts used in data analysis, version control of files and clear labelling of file types and revisions.

In line with the broader FAIR principles, the project also addresses outputs beyond datasets. Scientific publications will be deposited in open access, and code or scripts developed for data analysis will be shared under open-source licenses. Data security during the project is ensured through regular backups and institutional storage infrastructure. No personal or sensitive data are processed, and no ethical approvals are required, as all data originate from non-invasive experimental setups and public dissemination activities.

The project allocates the necessary resources—both technical and human—to support good data management throughout its lifecycle, with dedicated support from the hosting institution (Université de Bordeaux) and external infrastructure partners.

3. Other research outputs

- **In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).**
- **Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.**

In addition to research data, the TaphArt project will generate a number of other research outputs, primarily in digital form. These include data analysis scripts, image processing workflows, experimental protocols, and documentation for laboratory simulations related to environmental degradation processes. While the project does not produce software or physical outputs (such as biological samples or new materials), the digital research objects created will be managed according to the same FAIR principles as datasets.

All scripts and workflows developed for processing 3D images, hyperspectral data, or numerical analysis (e.g. statistical comparisons, time-series modeling) will be documented, versioned, and made openly available in open-source repositories such as Zenodo. These will include clear descriptions of dependencies, usage instructions, licensing terms (e.g. MIT or GPL), and links to example datasets when appropriate. Protocols for the experimental simulation of taphonomic processes will be provided as standalone documents (e.g. PDF or Markdown) and will be deposited alongside the datasets they support.

Metadata for these research outputs will include references to related datasets, the project's funding information (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101109977), and licensing conditions, ensuring they are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs) will be assigned to ensure long-term accessibility and citability. Where appropriate, qualified references to external standards or existing methods (e.g. those published in scientific literature or in public repositories like protocols.io) will also be included.

By managing these outputs transparently and openly, the project ensures that not only the data, but the entire analytical and experimental workflow, is reproducible and reusable by the research community—both during and beyond the project lifetime.

4. Allocation of resources

- **What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?**
- **How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)**
- **Who will be responsible for data management in your project?**
- **How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?**

Costs related to making data and other research outputs FAIR in the TaphArt project are limited but accounted for. They primarily include indirect costs associated with the time needed to document, prepare, and curate datasets, scripts, and protocols for open access deposition; as well as minor direct costs related to long-term storage and archiving in trusted repositories. No external data management service providers are involved.

These efforts are covered by personnel costs already budgeted in the project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) framework. This includes time allocated by the fellow for preparing data and metadata, documenting experimental workflows, and depositing outputs in repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala. The hosting institution, Université de Bordeaux, also provides in-kind support via its Research Data service and access to Huma-Num infrastructure for deposit in Nakala. These resources fall under eligible costs according to the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement.

The person responsible for data management is the MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow (Neemias Santos da Rosa), with support from the Université de Bordeaux Research Data Officer and technical assistance from the institutional IT and research support services.

Long-term preservation will be ensured through the selection of trusted, EOSC-compatible repositories that commit to multi-year storage and persistent access, such as Zenodo, Nakala, or a suitable ARIADNEplus node. These platforms ensure at least 10 years of data availability, with metadata guaranteed to remain available even if the datasets are withdrawn or archived.

The datasets to be preserved long-term include:

- All experimental datasets (raw and processed)
- Associated metadata and documentation
- Analysis scripts and protocols

The decision on what to retain is made by the fellow in coordination with the supervisor and based on the scientific value, potential for reuse, and compliance with Horizon Europe's open science guidelines. No significant financial investment is foreseen for long-term preservation, as the repositories selected offer free or publicly funded services for open-access projects. However, additional backup copies will be maintained on the institution's internal research data servers to provide redundancy and safeguard research integrity.

5. Data security

- **What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?**
- **Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?**

All research data generated during the TaphArt project will be managed using secure and reliable infrastructure provided by the Université de Bordeaux, which ensures compliance with institutional and European standards for data security. During the active phase of the project, data will be stored on institutional servers with regular automated backups, version control, and access-restricted folders when appropriate. In addition, data are also stored locally on encrypted, access-controlled devices used by the researcher, with periodic manual backups to secure drives.

Although the project does not involve sensitive or personal data, all files are handled with care to prevent loss, corruption, or unauthorized modification. No transfer of confidential or ethically regulated content is expected.

Once validated and prepared for publication, datasets will be transferred to trusted repositories for long-term preservation. These include Zenodo, Nakala (operated by Huma-Num), and possibly a disciplinary repository within ARIADNEplus, all of which guarantee secure storage, open access compliance, and persistent identifiers. These platforms ensure redundant storage, data integrity, and metadata preservation, meeting the requirements for Horizon Europe-funded projects.

The selected repositories are aligned with FAIR principles and provide the technical infrastructure necessary for long-term curation and data recovery. As a result, data security is ensured both during the project and after its completion, supporting sustainable and open research practices.

6. Ethics

- **Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).**
- **Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?**

There are no ethics or legal issues that impact data sharing in the TaphArt project. The research does not involve the collection or processing of personal data, nor does it include any data subject to ethical review (such as human participants, sensitive materials, or restricted cultural heritage content). All experimental procedures involve non-invasive analysis of materials created by the research team, and all dissemination materials (e.g. photographs or videos of outreach events) involve only project members or public audiences in open settings, with no collection of identifiable information.

As such, no informed consent for data sharing or preservation is required, and no personal or sensitive data are included in any dataset generated. This has been clearly stated in the ethics self-assessment submitted during the proposal phase, and confirmed in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethics deliverables are expected for this project, and the data management strategy fully complies with the legal and ethical framework of Horizon Europe, as well as the institutional policies of the Université de Bordeaux.

Should any unforeseen ethical or legal concerns arise (e.g. third-party copyright in dissemination materials), they will be addressed by applying appropriate licensing restrictions or access limitations, and by documenting these conditions transparently in the dataset metadata.

7. Other issues

- **Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?**

In addition to complying with Horizon Europe requirements and the FAIR principles, the TaphArt project also follows national and institutional procedures for data management:

- **Université de Bordeaux Research Data Policy:** The project aligns with the institutional guidelines on responsible research data management, as outlined by the Université de Bordeaux. This includes the use of secure storage infrastructure, good documentation practices, and the recommendation to deposit data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala (Huma-Num).
- **Huma-Num (TGIR) infrastructure:** As a project based in France and hosted by a public research institution, TaphArt has access to the national humanities data infrastructure Huma-Num, which provides long-term preservation services via Nakala, along with guidance on metadata and licensing. Use of Huma-Num services ensures alignment with French national recommendations on open science and digital humanities.
- **Open Science recommendations by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research:** The project contributes to the broader implementation of the French National Plan for Open Science, which promotes free access to research data, interoperability, and reusability, particularly for publicly funded research.

These procedures complement the Horizon Europe open science framework and help ensure the sustainability, legality, and reusability of the research outputs during and after the project.

Photographs and videos of dissemination activities carried out during the project

1. Data Summary

- **Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.**
- **What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?**
- **What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?**
- **What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?**
- **What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?**
- **To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?**

The dataset "DISSEM_MEDIA" includes photographs and videos produced as part of the TaphArt project's dissemination activities. These materials document outreach events, public presentations, and communication efforts carried out over the two-year project duration. All content is original and generated during the course of the project; no existing media is reused.

The files are saved in RAW, JPG, and MP4 formats, with an estimated total size of approximately 50 GB. The purpose of this

dataset is to provide visual and audiovisual support for science communication, public engagement, and institutional visibility. It reflects the project's commitment to open science and outreach by making its activities accessible to both academic and non-academic audiences.

The data is produced by the research team and communication units of the host institutions, primarily the Université de Bordeaux, during seminars, workshops, and field-based dissemination actions. This dataset will be useful to science communicators, outreach professionals, educators, and institutions interested in examples of effective public engagement strategies in European-funded research projects.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- **Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?**
- **Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.**
- **Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential reuse?**
- **Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?**

All datasets generated by the TaphArt project will be assigned a persistent identifier (DOI) upon deposit, ensuring stable and long-term accessibility. The primary repository foreseen is Zenodo, which automatically assigns DOIs and complies with OpenAIRE guidelines. In parallel, the project is exploring the use of Nakala, the French trusted repository operated by TGIR Huma-Num, which also supports DOI assignment through DataCite and offers long-term preservation on national infrastructure.

For datasets with high disciplinary value in archaeology (e.g. experimental imaging, geochemical analyses, context-specific datasets), the project will evaluate the possibility of depositing through a national node of ARIADNEplus, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS, UK) or DANS (Netherlands), depending on suitability and institutional agreements.

Rich metadata will be created for all datasets, including descriptive elements such as title, authorship, institutional affiliation, abstract, keywords, date and location of data collection, methodology, file formats, licensing, and funding references. Metadata will comply with the DataCite schema (Zenodo and Nakala) and, where applicable, will be aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM) for archaeological content. This ensures semantic interoperability and integration into disciplinary and general discovery platforms.

Keywords will be systematically provided to support discovery and reuse, with particular attention to terms relevant to Middle Stone Age archaeology, experimental rock art degradation, imaging techniques, and conservation science.

All metadata will be published openly and structured in machine-readable formats, ensuring compatibility with standard harvesting protocols such as OAI-PMH. This will enable indexing by OpenAIRE, EOSC, and other aggregators, guaranteeing that datasets are discoverable by both human users and automated services.

2.2.1. Making data accessible : Repository

- **Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?**
- **Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?**
- **Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?**

TaphArt datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories that meet the requirements for FAIR data, long-term accessibility, and OpenAIRE compliance. The primary repository chosen is Zenodo, maintained by CERN and supported by the European Commission. Zenodo is widely used by Horizon Europe projects, ensures robust infrastructure, immediate open access, and automatic DOI assignment.

In addition, the project will consider depositing in Nakala, the national repository for humanities and social sciences operated by TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS). Nakala is a certified repository based in France, providing stable hosting, persistent identifiers (via DataCite), and disciplinary support for research outputs in archaeology and cultural heritage.

For datasets of high archaeological relevance, especially those intended for international reuse or integration in heritage infrastructures, the project will evaluate deposition through the ARIADNEplus infrastructure via an appropriate national node, such as the Archaeology Data Service (ADS) or DANS. This option will be prioritized for datasets that benefit from enriched archaeological metadata and curation.

Exploratory steps have been taken to review the submission procedures, metadata requirements, and licensing conditions for Zenodo and Nakala. The project team is also initiating contacts with ARIADNEplus nodes to assess the feasibility of deposition. All repositories under consideration ensure that datasets are assigned a DOI, which is a persistent and resolvable identifier linking

directly to the dataset landing page, enabling durable access and citation.

2.2.2. Making data accessible : Data

- **Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.**
- **If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.**
- **Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?**
- **If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?**
- **How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?**
- **Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?**

All data generated by the TaphArt project will be made openly available as a matter of principle, in alignment with Horizon Europe's open science policies and the project's commitment to transparency, reproducibility, and societal impact. No legal, contractual, ethical, or privacy-related constraints apply to the datasets produced, as the project does not involve personal data or commercially sensitive information. All datasets are based on non-invasive experiments, scientific imaging, and dissemination activities involving consenting participants or publicly accessible materials.

An embargo period may be applied in selected cases to allow for the preparation and submission of peer-reviewed publications. In such cases, data will be made openly available at the time of submission of the related publication, in accordance with the project's data sharing policy. Embargo periods, if any, will not exceed six months from the time of data generation, and each dataset record will clearly indicate its availability date.

All data will be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol, such as HTTPS, ensuring open and unrestricted access via the landing page of the repository (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus node). Each dataset will include a persistent and resolvable DOI that points directly to a public record and download options, without the need for user registration or authentication.

Since all data are intended to be open access and no personal or sensitive data are processed, no restrictions on access are foreseen during or after the project. If exceptional access limitations arise (e.g. embargo, third-party copyright), the repository's access control features will be used to temporarily restrict access while providing appropriate metadata and contact information for users seeking early access.

The identity of users accessing the data will not be tracked, as the datasets will be fully open and do not require login or authentication. Download metrics may be collected by the repositories for statistical purposes only.

There is no need for a data access committee, as none of the datasets involve sensitive, personal, or ethically regulated content requiring evaluation of access requests.

2.2.3. Making data accessible : Metadata

- **Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?**
- **How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?**
- **Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?**

All metadata associated with the datasets produced by the TaphArt project will be made openly available and published under the CC0 public domain dedication, in compliance with the requirements of the Grant Agreement. This will allow for automatic indexing by platforms such as OpenAIRE and integration into disciplinary catalogues. Each metadata record will include a persistent identifier (DOI) and complete information enabling direct access to the corresponding dataset.

The metadata will include all necessary elements to facilitate access to and reuse of the datasets: title, authors, date, file formats, licensing terms, access protocol, storage location, embargo period (if applicable), and direct links to downloadable files.

All metadata records will explicitly indicate that the dataset was produced under the Horizon Europe TaphArt project (Grant Agreement No. 101109977), ensuring compliance with funder requirements and enabling automatic linkage via OpenAIRE.

The data will be preserved for a minimum of ten years, in accordance with European best practices and the retention policies of the selected repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or an ARIADNEplus node). Even in the event that a dataset must be withdrawn, the corresponding metadata record will remain available as a tombstone page, maintaining citation integrity and reference continuity. The project does not develop software as a standalone research product, but scripts and data processing code will be produced as part of the data analysis workflow. These scripts (e.g. for image processing, data normalization, or statistical comparison) will be

shared alongside the relevant datasets under open-source licenses such as MIT or GPL, and will be deposited in Zenodo, with persistent links included in the associated metadata records.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- **What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?**
- **In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?**
- **Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?**

The TaphArt project will ensure data interoperability by using well-established data formats, disciplinary metadata standards, and community-endorsed best practices. All datasets will be formatted in widely used and open formats such as CSV, XLSX, TIFF, JPG, RAW, MP4, ENVI, and HDF5, ensuring compatibility across platforms and disciplines.

Metadata will be structured using the DataCite schema (for Zenodo and Nakala) and, where appropriate, aligned with the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM), which is the community-endorsed standard for archaeological datasets. The ACDM provides semantic consistency and facilitates integration into broader infrastructures such as ARIADNEplus, OpenAIRE, and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). For tabular and numerical data, standard variable naming and unit conventions will be followed to maximize readability and compatibility.

In case the project generates project-specific vocabularies or uses non-standard terminologies (for instance, for experimental categories or environmental simulation parameters), a mapping to common ontologies will be provided when possible. These vocabularies or classifications will be openly published to enable reuse, refinement, and extension by other researchers.

Where relevant, datasets will include qualified references to other datasets produced within the project (e.g. linking image files to corresponding numerical analysis outputs) or to external datasets used as comparative baselines. These links will be established using persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs or URIs) and clearly described in the metadata to enable structured cross-referencing and semantic interoperability.

The project team is committed to following interoperability best practices promoted by the FAIR principles, including the use of machine-readable formats, standardized variable names, and clear licensing and provenance declarations.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- **How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?**
- **Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?**
- **Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?**
- **Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?**
- **Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.**
- **Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.**

To ensure maximum data re-use, the TaphArt project will provide comprehensive documentation alongside each dataset. This will include structured README files detailing the methodology, data collection context, file structure, variable definitions, units of measurement, software requirements (if applicable), and any data cleaning or transformation procedures applied. For numerical datasets, codebooks and examples of analytical workflows will be included. For imaging and video datasets, metadata will indicate acquisition parameters, equipment used, and pre/post-processing steps. All documentation will be in English and structured to support understanding and reuse by both domain experts and interdisciplinary users.

All datasets will be made freely available in the public domain under standard open licenses that permit broad reuse. The default license will be CC BY 4.0, unless there is a specific need to apply CC0 (for metadata or non-attributable content) or another recognized license. This licensing approach complies with the obligations set out in the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and ensures legal clarity for data reuse.

The datasets will be structured and documented in such a way that they remain usable by third parties, including after the project ends. Persistent identifiers (DOIs) will be assigned to all datasets, and hosting in trusted repositories (Zenodo, Nakala, or ARIADNEplus) will guarantee their long-term availability and accessibility, typically for at least 10 years.

Provenance will be fully documented using accepted metadata standards (e.g. DataCite, ACDM), indicating the origin of the data, institutions and researchers involved, instruments or software used, and processing history. When datasets derive from previous project outputs (e.g. linking raw image data to post-processed files or analysis tables), qualified references will be included to establish transparent data lineage.

The project will apply several data quality assurance measures: calibration of instruments and imaging systems prior to data acquisition, use of validated protocols for experiments and environmental simulation, consistency checks between datasets and documentation, peer-review of code/scripts used in data analysis, version control of files and clear labelling of file types and revisions.

In line with the broader FAIR principles, the project also addresses outputs beyond datasets. Scientific publications will be deposited in open access, and code or scripts developed for data analysis will be shared under open-source licenses. Data security during the project is ensured through regular backups and institutional storage infrastructure. No personal or sensitive data are processed, and no ethical approvals are required, as all data originate from non-invasive experimental setups and public dissemination activities.

The project allocates the necessary resources—both technical and human—to support good data management throughout its lifecycle, with dedicated support from the hosting institution (Université de Bordeaux) and external infrastructure partners.

3. Other research outputs

- **In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).**
- **Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.**

In addition to research data, the TaphArt project will generate a number of other research outputs, primarily in digital form. These include data analysis scripts, image processing workflows, experimental protocols, and documentation for laboratory simulations related to environmental degradation processes. While the project does not produce software or physical outputs (such as biological samples or new materials), the digital research objects created will be managed according to the same FAIR principles as datasets.

All scripts and workflows developed for processing 3D images, hyperspectral data, or numerical analysis (e.g. statistical comparisons, time-series modeling) will be documented, versioned, and made openly available in open-source repositories such as Zenodo. These will include clear descriptions of dependencies, usage instructions, licensing terms (e.g. MIT or GPL), and links to example datasets when appropriate. Protocols for the experimental simulation of taphonomic processes will be provided as standalone documents (e.g. PDF or Markdown) and will be deposited alongside the datasets they support.

Metadata for these research outputs will include references to related datasets, the project's funding information (Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101109977), and licensing conditions, ensuring they are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. Persistent identifiers (e.g. DOIs) will be assigned to ensure long-term accessibility and citability. Where appropriate, qualified references to external standards or existing methods (e.g. those published in scientific literature or in public repositories like protocols.io) will also be included.

By managing these outputs transparently and openly, the project ensures that not only the data, but the entire analytical and experimental workflow, is reproducible and reusable by the research community—both during and beyond the project lifetime.

4. Allocation of resources

- **What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?**
- **How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)**
- **Who will be responsible for data management in your project?**
- **How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?**

Costs related to making data and other research outputs FAIR in the TaphArt project are limited but accounted for. They primarily include indirect costs associated with the time needed to document, prepare, and curate datasets, scripts, and protocols for open access deposition; as well as minor direct costs related to long-term storage and archiving in trusted repositories. No external data management service providers are involved.

These efforts are covered by personnel costs already budgeted in the project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA)

framework. This includes time allocated by the fellow for preparing data and metadata, documenting experimental workflows, and depositing outputs in repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala. The hosting institution, Université de Bordeaux, also provides in-kind support via its Research Data service and access to Huma-Num infrastructure for deposit in Nakala. These resources fall under eligible costs according to the Horizon Europe Grant Agreement.

The person responsible for data management is the MSCA Postdoctoral Fellow (Neemias Santos da Rosa), with support from the Université de Bordeaux Research Data Officer and technical assistance from the institutional IT and research support services.

Long-term preservation will be ensured through the selection of trusted, EOSC-compatible repositories that commit to multi-year storage and persistent access, such as Zenodo, Nakala, or a suitable ARIADNEplus node. These platforms ensure at least 10 years of data availability, with metadata guaranteed to remain available even if the datasets are withdrawn or archived.

The datasets to be preserved long-term include:

- All experimental datasets (raw and processed)
- Associated metadata and documentation
- Analysis scripts and protocols

The decision on what to retain is made by the fellow in coordination with the supervisor and based on the scientific value, potential for reuse, and compliance with Horizon Europe's open science guidelines. No significant financial investment is foreseen for long-term preservation, as the repositories selected offer free or publicly funded services for open-access projects. However, additional backup copies will be maintained on the institution's internal research data servers to provide redundancy and safeguard research integrity.

5. Data security

- **What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?**
- **Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?**

All research data generated during the TaphArt project will be managed using secure and reliable infrastructure provided by the Université de Bordeaux, which ensures compliance with institutional and European standards for data security. During the active phase of the project, data will be stored on institutional servers with regular automated backups, version control, and access-restricted folders when appropriate. In addition, data are also stored locally on encrypted, access-controlled devices used by the researcher, with periodic manual backups to secure drives.

Although the project does not involve sensitive or personal data, all files are handled with care to prevent loss, corruption, or unauthorized modification. No transfer of confidential or ethically regulated content is expected.

Once validated and prepared for publication, datasets will be transferred to trusted repositories for long-term preservation. These include Zenodo, Nakala (operated by Huma-Num), and possibly a disciplinary repository within ARIADNEplus, all of which guarantee secure storage, open access compliance, and persistent identifiers. These platforms ensure redundant storage, data integrity, and metadata preservation, meeting the requirements for Horizon Europe-funded projects.

The selected repositories are aligned with FAIR principles and provide the technical infrastructure necessary for long-term curation and data recovery. As a result, data security is ensured both during the project and after its completion, supporting sustainable and open research practices.

6. Ethics

- **Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).**
- **Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?**

There are no ethics or legal issues that impact data sharing in the TaphArt project. The research does not involve the collection or processing of personal data, nor does it include any data subject to ethical review (such as human participants, sensitive materials, or restricted cultural heritage content). All experimental procedures involve non-invasive analysis of materials created by the research team, and all dissemination materials (e.g. photographs or videos of outreach events) involve only project members or public audiences in open settings, with no collection of identifiable information.

As such, no informed consent for data sharing or preservation is required, and no personal or sensitive data are included in any dataset generated. This has been clearly stated in the ethics self-assessment submitted during the proposal phase, and confirmed in the Description of the Action (DoA).

No ethics deliverables are expected for this project, and the data management strategy fully complies with the legal and ethical framework of Horizon Europe, as well as the institutional policies of the Université de Bordeaux.

Should any unforeseen ethical or legal concerns arise (e.g. third-party copyright in dissemination materials), they will be addressed by applying appropriate licensing restrictions or access limitations, and by documenting these conditions transparently in the dataset metadata.

7. Other issues

- **Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?**

In addition to complying with Horizon Europe requirements and the FAIR principles, the TaphArt project also follows national and institutional procedures for data management:

- **Université de Bordeaux Research Data Policy:** The project aligns with the institutional guidelines on responsible research data management, as outlined by the Université de Bordeaux. This includes the use of secure storage infrastructure, good documentation practices, and the recommendation to deposit data in trusted repositories such as Zenodo and Nakala (Huma-Num).
- **Huma-Num (TGIR) infrastructure:** As a project based in France and hosted by a public research institution, TaphArt has access to the national humanities data infrastructure Huma-Num, which provides long-term preservation services via Nakala, along with guidance on metadata and licensing. Use of Huma-Num services ensures alignment with French national recommendations on open science and digital humanities.
- **Open Science recommendations by the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research:** The project contributes to the broader implementation of the French National Plan for Open Science, which promotes free access to research data, interoperability, and reusability, particularly for publicly funded research.

These procedures complement the Horizon Europe open science framework and help ensure the sustainability, legality, and reusability of the research outputs during and after the project.